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AUTHOR:	Ioanna Panagea (EV-ILVO), Guillaume Blanchy (EV-ILVO), Katharina Keiblinger (BOKU), Mariangela Diacono (CREA), Christoph Rosinger (BOKU), Paul Quataert (EV-ILVO), Claudia Di Bene (CREA), Sophia Götzinger (AGES), Lisa Makoschitz (AGES), Taru Sandén (AGES), Heide Spiegel (AGES), María Alonso-Ayuso (CSIC), Laura B. Martinez-Garcia (CSIC), Jorge Álvaro-Fuentes (CSIC), Marjetka Suhadolc (ULBF), Kristina Ocvirk (ULBF), Sonja Kay (AGS), Valerie Viaud (INRAE), Sophie Drexler (Thünen), Felix Seidel (Thünen), Axel Don (Thünen), Greet Ruyschaert (EV-ILVO).
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Name	Institute
Heide Spiegel, Lisa Makoschitz, Taru Sandén	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES), AT
Juliane Hirte, Shiva Ghiasi, Christoph Pfeil	Agroscope (AGS), CH
Eszter Tóth	Centre for Agricultural Research (ATK), HU
Johannes L. Jensen	Aarhus University (AU), DK
Katharina Keiblinger	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, (BOKU), AT
Huyghebaert Bruno	Centre Wallon de Recherches Agronomiques (CRAW), BE
Antonio Bruno, Claudia Di Bene, Silvia Vanino, Mariangela Diacono, Lorenzo D'Avino	Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA), IT
Karin Kauer	Estonian University of Life Sciences, (EMU), EE
Maarten De Boever, Ioanna Panagea, Paul Pardon, Tommy D'Hose, Kaat Mertens	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (EV-ILVO), BE
Denis Stajanko	University of Maribor, (FKBV), SI
César Plaza, Jorge Alvaro-Fuentes, María Alonso-Ayuso, Jose L Gabriel, Santín-Montanyá M.I.	National Institute for Agriculture and Food Research and Technology - Higher Council for Scientific Research (INIA-CSIC), ES
Grzegorz Siebielec	Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation (IUNG), PL
Corina Carranca, Maria da Conceição Gonçalves, Nádia Castanheira	National Institute for Agrarian and Veterinarian Research I. P. (INIAV), PT
Valérie Viaud, Katja Klumpp	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement (INRAE), FR
Ieva Mockeviciene, Monika Vilkiene, Feiza Virginijus	Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry (LAMMC), LT
Teresa G. Bárcena, Trond M. Henriksen	Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO), NO
Nargish Parvin, Martin Bolinder, Thomas Kätterer	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), SE
Ülfet Erdal, Zeynep Demir	Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Livestock, General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies (TAGEM), TR
Anna Jacobs, Felix Seidel, Florian Schneider, Sophie Drexler, Daria Seitz	Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture (Thünen), DE
Kristina Ocvirk, Marjetka Suhadolc, Rok Mihelič	University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Centre for Soil and Environmental Science (ULBF), SI
Ava Gillikin, Loes Verdonk, Chantal Hendriks	Wageningen University & Research (WUR), NL

Executive summary

The storage of soil organic carbon (SOC) can be influenced by humans through various management options such as land use, cropping practices, crop types, irrigation, fertilization, tillage, and other land management activities. By adopting appropriate land management options, agricultural systems can contribute to mitigate climate change by reducing carbon (C) loss from soils or even sequester C in soils. This can be achieved by promoting practices that enhance C inputs to the soil and improve C quality of these inputs, thereby removing atmospheric carbon dioxide, or by reducing C turnover.

The EJP SOIL-CarboSeq project aims to assess the potential of European agricultural soils to sequester C, considering biological, technical, and economic constraints. Specifically, the project's WP2 on crop management focused on quantifying potential C sequestration across different pedo-climatic regions and agricultural management options in European croplands.

This report provides quantitative estimates of the impact of seven agricultural measures on changes in SOC stocks in Europe. These so-called emission factors (EFs) will be utilized in CarboSeq by WP8 to spatially explicitly evaluate the C sequestration potential of European agricultural land by multiplying the EFs with the identified area of implementation based on the abovementioned constraints.

The estimation of robust and representative EFs can be achieved by carefully compiling measured data from long-term field experiments (LTEs). The methodology used to collect, validate, and store the data from European LTEs is presented in chapter 2 –[WP2 data management system](#), with details on the resources, the database structure, template, and tools. The data collection, validation, and adequate storage in a common database promoted consistency and effective sharing but was challenging and laborious. Nevertheless, such a data management system promoted effective collaboration and sharing of information, it safeguarded the data and allowed for open access and ensured that the dataset complies with the necessary quality standards.

From this data collection, estimates of the different EFs for each management option were derived alongside significant pedoclimatic and management predictors for each option. The methodology to estimate and analyse the C stocks and EFs allowed to gain valuable insights on the potential of C sequestration in European cropland soils and is presented in chapter 3 - [Definition, description, and ways of estimating emission factors](#). The harmonized methodology applied to estimate and analyse the EFs allows for a consistent comparison and interpretation of the results across the considered agricultural management options.

The derived EFs are presented and evaluated per management option. It was found that all the management options that were considered have the potential to increase the SOC in European croplands but in most cases the availability and distribution of data did not allow for deriving unique EFs per climatic zone. The option to grow cover crops versus no cover crops presented

in chapter 4 - [Cover Crops](#) can lead to a SOC increase up to 6%. The option to increase the share of forage legumes in the crop rotation which is presented in chapter 5 - [Crops and crop diversification](#) can yield to an increase of SOC stocks up to 13 Mg ha⁻¹ depending on how much more forage legumes will be included in the rotation and on the C stocks of the control management option. Incorporating the previous crop's residues instead of removing these (chapter 6 - [Crop residues](#)) can also lead to increased SOC stocks with the magnitude of this increase to depend on the C stock of the control option, the clay content of the soil, the rainfall and the amount of cereals that are included in the rotation. The options to not invert the soil with tillage and no tillage compared with inversion tillage can lead up to 5% and 14 % more SOC respectively (chapter 7 - [Tillage](#)). For the option to irrigate the crops compared to rainfed systems in chapter 8 - [Irrigation](#) was not possible to estimate EFs because of lack of European LTEs on the topic. Finally, the option to incorporate hedges and single trees in lines within the field as agroforestry options, presented in chapter 9 - [Agroforestry](#) the higher potential for SOC increase, up to 26% when compared to croplands without trees.

The summary of the developed EFs and the ranges of important variables considered in the analyses are presented in chapter 11- [General conclusions](#), while their validity, and robustness are outlined and discussed in chapter 10 - [General outlook](#). The use of EFs is a standardized and cost-effective approach for estimating the impact of agricultural management practices on C sequestration in soils e.g., in national greenhouse gas inventories following Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) guidelines. However, EFs have limitations in accurately capturing the temporal dynamic of SOC with C sequestration rates (C sequestration or C loss mitigation) and may lead to overestimation or underestimation of the effects. Moreover, they do not consider initial SOC stocks and cannot fully account for environmental and management variability. Complementing EFs with additional information, such as data from LTEs and on soil properties and climate conditions, can enhance the accuracy and robustness of estimated SOC stock changes and improve understanding of the effectiveness of management practices for C sequestration.

Effects of different crop management options on SOC stocks and deriving emission factors

The **CARBSEQ** approach based on European LTEs

Emission factor estimation

$$EF_{relative} = \frac{SOC\ Stock_{treatment}}{SOC\ Stock_{control}}$$

Where

$EF_{relative}$ stands for the emission factor of a measurement

$SOC\ stock\ treatment$ is the SOC stock as measured at a specific moment and sampling depth in the management option under evaluation (treatment)

$SOC\ stock\ control$ is the SOC stock as measured at the same moment and same soil depth in the control option.

Emission factors for different crop management options

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1. Introduction

Land use and management of agricultural systems have been known to affect the soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks through changes in land use, cropping practices (intensity and types of crops), irrigation, fertilization, tillage, and other management activities. Consequently, land use and land management can potentially be used to reduce greenhouse gas emissions or even uptake carbon (C) by promoting practices that increase C input to the soil, thus, increasing atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) uptake and incorporation in the soil.

The aim of the EJP SOIL-CarboSeq project is to estimate the feasible C sequestration potential in Europe considering biophysical, technical and economical constrains. The members of WP2 working on- crop management aimed to quantify C sequestration across pedo-climatic regions and farming conditions by changing crop management practices in European croplands. This report presents quantitative estimates of the effect of seven established and known agricultural measures on the SOC stock changes in Europe by estimating emission factors (EFs) based on long-term field experiments (LTEs). These EFs will be used by the Carboseq WP8 (Building Scenarios for C Sequestration) to assess the C sequestration potential using the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Tier 2 approach (emission factor x activity data) (IPCC 2006, 2006). Currently, the EFs for the different management activities on croplands which are used for similar analyses are derived from the IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories (IPCC, 2019) including Tier 1 global default EFs for mineral soils for tillage (full, reduced, no-till), input (low, medium and high levels of residue return and manure), set-aside, and land use conversion from grassland or forest.

Crops are the key source of C input to the soil via aboveground biomass residues, root biomass, and root exudates. EFs were estimated through a European wide data collection to quantify the C sequestration potential by cover crops, crop diversification, crop residues, and agroforestry. In drier regions and regions that will suffer from more frequent drought spells in summer, C-input is limited by moisture deficits, and irrigation will affect both on C-input and SOC-turnover. This turnover is also affected by soil tillage operations. Thus, EFs for these two management options are also reported.

Data and metadata from European LTEs published in the literature, existing databases and metaanalyses as well as through personal communication with the LTE owners was collected following the logical model of the workflow of WP2 (Figure 1-1). This data was collected in structured harmonized templates, and quality control of the data, both manually and through an automatic error detection tool, was conducted. Then, the completed and checked templates were included in the database created by the CarboSeq WP2 task named "CarboSeq crop and soil management database". Through an export module, users could explore, filter, query, and export the data required for analysis.

Figure 1-1: Logical model of workflow of the CarboSeq WP2.

This report presents the methodology used to collect, store, and utilize the data and metadata (chapter 2), and to analyse the information (chapter 3). The results are organized in six main sections, one for each group of management options: cover crops (chapter 4), crop rotations and diversification (chapter 5), crop residues (chapter 6), tillage (chapter 7), irrigation (chapter 8) and agroforestry (chapter 9). Finally, the limitations and discussion are presented in chapter 10 and the summary of the EF to be used in chapter 11. Appendix I provides detailed information, data, and metadata for the considered experiments in the analysis of each management option that were used to derive EFs.

2. WP2 data management system

Publishing data involves several sub-processes which include the collection, preparation, storage, publishing and maintenance of the data and meta-data (European Data Portal, 2018). Within WP2 a data management system was created to allow a complete and harmonized collection of data and metadata related to the different tasks' management options in a way that information is practical, easy to access and explore and downloadable in a format that expedites their analysis. The physical model of the data management system is presented in Figure 2-1 and is described in the following sections.

Figure 2-1: Physical model of the data management system. The red arrows refer to the data input workflow and the blue arrows to the data output workflow.

2.1. Collecting and compiling data sources

The metadata of different publication types with potentially relevant European LTEs for the CarboSeq tasks and other CarboSeq WPs found via the EJP SOIL task 7.3 database with meta data of European LTEs (Blanchy et al., 2023b) existing databases of meta-analyses (e.g., Haddaway et al., 2015; Sandén et al., 2018) via the web of science or via the partners, were compiled in an online spreadsheet. Each publication (from now on called 'Entry') was linked to a spreadsheet template where all the meta-data and data about the experiment(s) included in the publication were stored (see Section 2.2). Each entry was assigned to one of the project partners who had to evaluate if the publication is relevant for CarboSeq, extract the required information, fill out the spreadsheet template, specify in the entry's online spreadsheet for which tasks and/or WPs is the specific entry possibly relevant and do the primary quality control check using the automatic template control check tool. The tool for the automatic template check (Blanchy, 2022) is accessible on GitHub (<https://github.com/CarboSeq/tools>), in the form of a Python script inside a Jupyter Notebook. The automatic check included checking the type

of the values, if a value was inside the drop-down list or if it was a new choice added by the user. The automatic script also checked for the consistency of the index across the different tables of the template and their uniqueness.

After this primary quality control, the partners related to the different tasks checked the entries that had been specified as possibly relevant for their specific task and performed a secondary quality control check. At this point, entries that were referring to the same experiment were merged into a single excel template. As soon as the templates were completed and checked the database curators merged these into one database. After the merge, several post processing quality checks were conducted, and flags were raised for entries that were having close or wrong coordinates or same experiment identities that potentially were referring to the same experiment and had to be merged. Entries in which there were no treatments specified were also flagged and checked manually afterwards. At this stage, for each experiment information about the climatic conditions were added. The climate data, derived from the worldwide raster files provided by WorldClim (~1 km²) (Fick and Hijmans, 2017), the “Global Aridity Index and Potential Evapotranspiration Climate Database v2” dataset (Trabucco and Robert, 2018), (Figure 2-2) and the Biogeographical regions dataset which contains the official delineations used in the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and for the EMERALD Network set up under the Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats (Bern Convention) of the European Environmental Agency (EEA, 2016) (Figure 2-3).

Figure 2-2: Aridity index map of Europe. (Taken from (Trabucco and Robert, 2018))

Table 2-1: Generalized climate classification scheme for Aridity Index Values (UNEP, 1997)

Aridity index value	Aridity class
< 0.03	Hyper Arid
0.03-0.2	Arid
0.2-0.5	Semi-Arid
0.5-0.65	Dry sub-humid
>0.65	Humid

Figure 2-3: Biogeographical regions in Europe (source (EEA, 2016))

2.2. Template and database description

After careful evaluation of the structure of several existing databases and starting from the template proposed for the online database with meta-data of European LTEs ((Blanchy et al., 2023b)), a template for the CarboSeq WP2 was created. The template (Blanchy et al., 2023a) is accessible on the CarboSeq community of the Zenodo repository in the form of a spreadsheet (<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8094887>). The vocabulary used in the template was mainly taken from the Knowledge Library of the Bonares project (<https://klibrary.bonares.de>) that implements standards such as WRB/USDA (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015), and FAO-AGROVOC thesaurus (<http://www.fao.org/agrovoc/>). Drop-down menus were used, when possible, to enforce a controlled common terminology with the possibility of adding new terms by the users.

The template, which is also compatible with the EJP SOIL task 7.3 template, is structured into different sheets. The use of unique IDs (indices) enables to make links between different sheets and allows the transformation of the CarboSeq WP2 template into the relational database where each sheet of the spreadsheet template corresponds to a database table. The “Readme” sheet includes information on how the template should be filled and the sheet “description” on the terms and definitions used. In the sheet “experiment” information about the experiments location and type are included and, in the sheet, “reference” the available publications per experiment and the contact details of the people who added the data are included. The details of the soil type are included in the sheet “soil-type” and description of the different treatments of the experiment in the sheet “treatment”. In the sheet “treatment” one row corresponds to the unique combination of levels of the varied factors. The different management operations that take place in the experiment are described in different sheets of the template as follows: Information about the tillage operations, the crop types and rotations, the amendments applied, and the irrigation schemes are included in the sheets “tillage”, “crops”, “amendment” and “irrigation” respectively. Finally, two sheets are included for collecting the results of crop and soil measurements and the related meta-data. In the sheet “data-crop” data about the crop yield and residues quality and quantity are included. In the sheet “data-soil” the data and meta-data about SOC, soil bulk density (BD), and soil pH, are presented in each row per soil depth layer and sampling year.

In each of the above-mentioned sheets three different categories of data and meta-data were defined: 1) **obligatory data** which refer to fields that had to be filled so that the database is functional and to enable one-to-many relationships (e.g., Experiment ID, Treatment ID etc.), 2) **important data** which referred to the minimum data requirements (e.g., soil sampling depth, sampling year, experiments coordinates) and 3) **useful data** which refer to information that are useful for the data analysis and results interpretation and, if available, would be valuable to be added.

The use of a structured template in a spreadsheet format has the advantage that most users are accustomed to this format and at the same time guarantees a level of consistency by only allowing specific data types and fixed terms enforced by using drop down menus. An advantage of this relational structure compared to templates with a unique table, is that it enables one-to-many relationships to be collected in a structured way, without creating excessive replications.

Subsequently, the CarboSeq crop and soil management database which is compatible with WP2 template was created. The structure of the database scheme (UML diagram) is shown in Figure 2-4. The different elements of each table, the different data types and the keys are presented. Note that it is the combination of ID (e.g., Experiment ID, Treatment ID, Rotation) that enables one to join a sheet with another one. Indeed, the Treatment ID might not be unique in the treatment table but is enforced to be unique within each Experiment ID.

Figure 2-4: Structure of the CarboSeq crop and soil management database scheme designed for the CarboSeq WP2 data collection (UML diagram). The tables with blue colour include the basic information and metadata of the experiments, the tables in green are used to store the information about the different management practices that take place in the experiment, and the orange tables are used to store the measured soil and crop data.

2.3. Export module

The export module is a tool designed to explore the data and export the required information in multiple formats suitable for further data exploration and analysis. It allows to query and filter the database to find existing data to answer specific scientific questions.

The export module is composed of multiple tabs. After loading the latest version of the database (.xlsx file) using the 'Upload' button or copying the Google Sheet URL, a map with the locations of the data collected is plotted and the following tabs automatically appear:

Filtering: filters the entire dataset according to user-defined criteria. The filtered dataset will then be used in the following tabs (i.e., Query, Export, Selection).

Query: helps to define pairs of 'Treatment ID' within the same 'Experiment ID' in which one is the 'reference' (or 'control') and the other differs from it by the chosen search criteria. The database does not contain any explicit and structured information about the factors to be investigated, instead it works by collecting information about the combination of levels itself (=one Treatment ID). For instance, it is not explicitly mentioned that an experiment investigates the factor 'tillage'; rather, the two levels (e.g., 'conventional' vs 'zero tillage') will be encoded when defining the metadata associated with 'tillage' ('tillage' table) for each Treatment ID within the Experiment ID. Great attention was paid to grant the flexibility to define specific research questions to the user, who can query and identify all experiments that could potentially contribute to answer the user's research questions.

Export: enables to export the selections made in the Filtering or Query tabs in 2 different formats (1. "Filtered DB" format which is an .xlsx file with similar tab structure as the template and / or 2. a "Flat DB" format which is an .xlsx file with one single tab in which the information is stacked).

Selection: enables exporting a selection of predefined experiments and treatments uploaded as an excel file with two columns ('Experiment ID' and 'Treatment ID') or three columns ('Experiment ID', 'Treatment ID_C' i.e., ID of the control, 'Treatment ID_T' i.e., ID of the treatment). The database is filtered accordingly, and the data are available in the 2 different formats.

The detailed instructions and examples on the use of the export module, the notebook for the export module and the export module tool are accessible on the CarboSeq community in the Zenodo repository (Blanchy, 2022) and GitHub (<https://github.com/CarboSeq/tools>).

2.4. Maintaining and storing data

During the project lifetime the database is updated frequently by the database curators and different versions are created. The database and the export module are fully functional and tested.

The CarboSeq crop and soil management database will continue to be maintained and fed with data until the end of the project. During the project, the partners were using the database at different times, therefore, different versions were created accordingly. Each version has a unique DOI (Digital Object Identifier). The different versions of the database (Ruyschaert et al., 2023) are stored under embargo in the Zenodo community of CarboSeq (https://zenodo.org/communities/ejp_soil_CarboSeq/?page=1&size=20). After analysis and publishing results, and the latest 6 months after the end of the project (31st July 2025) the embargo will be lifted, and the data will become open access. In case of a possible project extension, this embargo will be adjusted accordingly.

2.5. Database use

The CarboSeq crop and soil management database (version 07.07.2023, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8130195, <https://zenodo.org/record/8130195>,) contains about 500 entries (experiments) distributed in most of the European countries (Figure 2-5), but with a higher density in the countries of the EJP SOIL consortium which substantially contributed to the data collection.

The database is used by the WP2 partners to explore and collect the required data for calculating the EFs required for the estimation of the C sequestration potential for the considered management options in the soils of European agricultural land. Also, 67 LTEs from Germany were transferred from the CarboSeq crop and soil management database to the meta-database of European LTEs (EJP SOIL task 7.3 (Blanchy et al., 2023b)) with agreement of national coordinators. This was made possible due to the standardization of the templates used in both activities (CarboSeq WP2 and EJP Soil task 7.3). Also, the database is used by the other WPs of the CarboSeq as it contains valuable supporting information for the tasks WP3 Biochar and other soil amendments, WP4 Grassland management and WP9 Estimating C sequestration potentials.

Figure 2-5: Distribution of the experiments in the CarboSeq crop and soil management database (version 07.07.2023) across Europe

3. Definition, description, and ways of estimating emission factors.

The main goal of CarboSeq WP2- Crop management, was to estimate and derive EFs for the considered agricultural management options based on LTEs data in Europe. FAO, (2015a) and Guidelines (IPCC 2006, 2006) define EFs as “coefficients that quantify the emissions or removals of a gas per unit activity data. EFs are based on samples of measurements, averaged at various levels of detail depending upon the Tier methodology used, to develop a representative rate of emission for a given activity level under a given set of operating conditions”.

The IPCC provides guidelines on how to estimate EFs for different agricultural practices. EFs are typically calculated using LTEs data, where different management practices are tested and the resulting changes in SOC stocks (normally up to a depth of 30 cm) are measured over time.

To estimate EFs, a reference scenario needs to be defined, which is typically the management practice that is currently being used in the area or the baseline practice against which other practices are being compared. The change in SOC stocks resulting from the implementation of the alternative management practice is then calculated and expressed as a ratio of the SOC stocks in the reference scenario. This ratio is referred to as the EF. The relative EF is referred in literature also as C response ratio or management factor (Ogle et al., 2005).

3.1. Estimation of emission factors

In CarboSeq the IPCC method which uses a relative stock change factor (dimensionless) was applied to estimate EFs describing changes in SOC stocks. This Relative EF indicates a relative change in SOC stocks in the management option under evaluation (treatment) compared to a control option (Equation 1). Relative change higher than 1 corresponds to SOC stock increase in the considered management option in comparison to the control option while relative change to lower than 1 is a SOC stock decrease.

It is important to note that EFs are specific to the soil type, climate, and other site-specific factors of the location where the experiment was conducted. Therefore, EFs cannot be directly extrapolated to other locations without considering these site-specific factors.

$$EF_{relative} = \frac{SOC_Stock_{treatment}}{SOC_Stock_{control}} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

Where $EF_{relative}$ stands for the emission factor of a measurement, $SOC_stock_{treatment}$ is the SOC stocks as measured at a specific moment and sampling depth in the management option under evaluation (treatment) and $SOC_stock_{control}$ is the SOC stocks as measured at the same moment and same soil depth in the control option.

3.2. Estimation of carbon Stocks

Using measured bulk density (BD) and SOC concentration

If measured data for C concentration and BD were available, the relevant SOC stocks were estimated using Equation 2:

$$C_{stock} (Mg.ha^{-1}) = C_{conc} (g.kg^{-1}) * BD (Mg.m^{-3}) * soil\ depth (cm) * 0.1 \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

Where C_{stock} is the C stocks in a specific soil layer, C_{conc} represents the C concentration as measured in that soil layer, BD stands for bulk density at this soil layer and $soil\ depth$ represents the soil layer depth within that the C stocks are estimated and 0.1 is a units' conversion factor.

Using estimated BD from pedotransfer functions (PTF)

The PTF proposed in (Hollis et al., 2012) (Equation 3), was used to estimate the BD when measured values were not available. The particle size boundaries used in the dataset for the estimation of the specific PTF are for sand: 0.063-2 mm, silt: 0.002-0.063 mm and clay <0.002 mm.

$$BD(Mg.m^{-3}) = 0.80806 + (0.823844 * e^{-0.27993*OC\%}) + (0.0014065 * Sand\ \%) - (0.0010299 * Clay\ \%) \quad (\text{Eq.3})$$

where BD stands for bulk density, OC represents the organic C content in % in the layer of which the BD is estimated, $Sand$ and $Clay$ represent the sand and clay content percentage at this soil layer.

The BD was calculated separately for the control and the treatment. Then the Equation 2 was used to calculate the estimated C stocks.

In the case that the textural properties were not known, the clay and sand percentages required to estimate the BD were derived from the LUCAS topsoil physical properties for Europe (Ballabio et al., 2016).

Using equivalent soil mass approach

Alternatively, for the tillage task (Chapter 7), stocks were also calculated using equivalent soil mass approach (Lee et al., 2009). Several soil management options tend to increase or decrease BD of the treatment especially when measures also increase SOC. This can introduce an error when soil is sampled to a fixed depth. An alternative approach to the fixed depth stocks calculation is therefore to use the soil mass as a correction.

The mass of soil for both treatment and control is calculated as:

$$M_i \text{ (Mg. ha}^{-1}\text{)} = BDi \text{ (Mg. m}^3\text{)} * Ti \text{ (cm)} * 10^2 \quad (\text{Eq.4})$$

The difference among the treatment and control is then calculated as:

$$M_{i,add} = |M_{i,eq} - M_i| \quad (\text{Eq.5})$$

The C_{stock} for the treatment is then calculated depending on whether we have compaction or decompaction in the sampled layer of the treatment compared to the control:

For decompaction ($BD_t < BD_c$) (Eq.6)

$$C_{Stocki,equiv} = C_{Stocki,fixed} - C_{contop} * M_{i-1,add} + C_{conbottom} * (M_{i,add} + M_{i-1,add})$$

For compaction ($BD_t > BD_c$) (Eq.7)

$$C_{Stocki,equiv} = C_{Stocki,fixed} + C_{contop} * M_{i-1,add} + C_{conbottom} * (M_{i,add} + M_{i-1,add})$$

3.3. Analysis methodology of emission factors

The steps followed to estimate and analyse the EFs for each option are shown in Figure 3-1 and are described below.

For each available pair of control and treatment in an experiment, the relevant EF was estimated. The complete dataset of EFs was created following the order: where possible measured values were used (SOC stocks or SOC concentrations plus measured BD), if the BD was not available, the required SOC stocks were estimated based on the PTF and measured texture. When no data on texture nor BD measurements existed, the required SOC stocks were estimated based on the PTF and LUCAS texture.

To derive the most significant pedoclimatic and management predictors for the obtained relative EFs, we created different models. When it was decided to include in the dataset only one pair of control and treatment from each experiment (approach followed normally in meta-analyses), multiple linear regression was used (e.g. for Crop Residues – Chapter 6), while when the dataset included more than one pair of control and treatment within the same experiment linear mixed effects modelling (LMM) was used with the experiment ID as a random factor, to account for the interdependences among the same experiments.

Before selecting the best fitting or/and the most meaningful and applicable model for each management option, the available dataset was explored to identify correlations among the different variables to be possibly used, and for data limitations such as limited / unbalanced data across different climatic zones or soil types. The different predictor variables which at the end were considered in the analysis of each management option are presented in the respective chapter. (Chapter 4 - Chapter 9).

Figure 3-1: Steps followed for the estimation and analysis of the emission factors.

4. Cover Crops

Katharina Keiblinger¹, Mariangela Diacono², Christoph Rosinger^{1,3}

¹ University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, Department of Forest and Soil Sciences, Institute of Soil Research, 1190 Vienna, Austria

² Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Research Centre for Agriculture and Environment, 70125 Bari, Italy

³ University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, Department of Crop Sciences, Institute of Agronomy, 3430 Tulln an der Donau, Austria

4.1. Introduction

The cultivation of cover crops is an effective management measure to increase the C-input to arable soils potentially increasing the SOC stocks (Poepflau and Don, 2015). However, it is not clear if this is the case across multiple biomes. Moreover, LTEs from European field trials have not been uniformed and lack a comparable basis in terms of experimental design and control treatment. This is a crucial prerequisite to identify the C sequestration potential of this agricultural practice over Europe. Here, we evaluated the long-term C sequestration potential by growing cover crops versus no cover crops in European agro-ecosystems by calculating EFs based on European LTEs.

4.2. Methodology

We extracted data from the CarboSeq crop and soil management database (version 2022_10_03, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8127976, <https://zenodo.org/record/8127976>) following the two main prerequisites: (1) the only difference between the control treatment and the cover crop treatment is the cultivation of cover crops; any other factors (rotation of main crops, tillage, fertilization, etc.) had to be the same; (2) cover crops must be grown at least in 50% of the rotation (e.g., in a four-year rotation should be two times covers crops cultivated); (3) data have to come from annual cropping systems; (4) the minimum time of experimental duration has to be five years. This resulted in 13 experiments with a total of 27 pairs of control (without cover crops) and treatment (with cover crops). These experiments are distributed between southern Sweden in the north and central Spain in the south and mainly cover the continental and Atlantic climate zones (Figure 4-1). The calculation of relative EFs is based on the latest SOC stocks (Mg ha^{-1}) available (i.e., latest datapoint) of the LTE following the methodology proposed in Chapter 3. The relative EFs were calculated as the quotient of SOC stocks in the cover crop treatment over the control treatment.

Figure 4-1: Map of long-term cover crop trials across Europe used to determine emission factors (the colour legend indicates relative emission factors)

To derive the most significant environmental and management predictor for the obtained relative EFs, we applied LMM. An a priori LMM was conducted to evaluate whether the experimental duration or the measured soil depth had an effect on the relative EFs. This was important since these two factors varied between experiments and could bias further analyses. For the main LMMs, we used the following parameters: cover crop diversity (single species, species mixtures), soil amendments (no, inorganic, organic, both), tillage system (inversion, non-inversion), soil texture class (sandy loam, silt/silt clay loam and loam), aridity class (humid, dry sub-humid, semi-arid) and climatic zone (Continental, Atlantic, Mediterranean, Boreal). The restricted maximum likelihood estimation was chosen for LMM, with the Satterthwaite approximation for defining the degrees of freedom (Luke, 2017). We conducted a forward selection of parameters prior to obtaining the best-fitting model to select the most significant predictors. In this regard, other environmental parameters such as longitude, latitude, mean

annual precipitation or mean annual temperature showed a relatively lower predictive power. An one-way ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey test was further conducted to investigate significant differences within subgroups of parameters that turned out to be significant predictors of EFs as evaluated by LMM.

4.3. Results

Data exploration

A summary of the different variables in the selected dataset is shown in Table 4-1. Overall, the mean experimental duration was around 10 years, with only a few studies showing longer experimental durations (Figure 4-2a). Most studies have sampled to a soil depth of minimum 20 cm (Figure 4-2b). The clay content was evenly distributed between 15-30% (Figure 4-2c), and the SOC stock of the control of the 27 experimental observations was mainly between 0.3-2.7 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (Figure 4-2d).

Single cover crops were used in 13 experimental observations, while 14 observations used cover crop mixtures. The main cover crops used were rye grass (*Lolium p.*), winter vetch (*Vicia v.*), radish (*Raphanus sp.*), oat (*Avena s.*) and mustard (*Sinapis sp.*; *Brassica sp.*). Most studies (18 out of 27) used inorganic fertilizer, while organic fertilizers were used in seven experiments. Moreover, there was no significant difference between EFs calculated with measured bulk densities or with bulk densities derived from pedo-transfer functions. This is shown in Figure 4-3, testing data of measured bulk densities or SOC stocks against calculated bulk densities or SOC stocks.

Figure 4-2: The distribution of experimental observations ($n=27$) across (a) experimental duration, (b) soil sampling depth, (c) clay content and (d) SOC stock of the control. The black line indicates the average-fitted distribution.

Table 4-1: Summary of the different variables in our selected dataset

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
Sampling depth (cm)	10	31.4	24.2
Experiment duration (years)	5	38	11.33
SOC stock of the control ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	0.29	2.74	1.46
Clay content (%)	9	45	19.4
Annual precipitation (mm)	386	929	695
Annual mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	5.3	15.0	10.4
Average aridity index	0.247	1.262	0.758
Relative emission factor	0.98	1.19	1.06

Figure 4-3: The relationship between emission factors calculated with the measured BD and emission factors calculated with bulk densities based on pedo-transfer functions (Wilcoxon rank-sum test, $Z=-0.153$, $p=0.878$).

Relative emission factors

Overall, the mean relative EF across all observations was **1.06 (SE=±0.02, SD=±0.08)**, which is significantly higher than 1 (no change) ($T=4.022$, $p=0.001$; as revealed by paired sample t-test). The mean experimental duration was **11.3 (±1.34) years**.

A-priori LMM ($F=200.664$, $p<0.001$) revealed that neither experimental duration ($F=0.143$, $p=0.709$), sampling depth ($F=0.00$, $p=0.945$) nor the SOC of the control (in $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; $F=0.015$, $p=0.904$) had a significant impact on the obtained EFs.

The final model ($F=217.642$, $p<0.001$) revealed soil amendment type and climatic zone as significant predictors of the obtained relative EFs (Figure 4-4). Cover crop diversity, tillage system, soil texture class and aridity class had no significant predictive power.

Table 4-2: Results of a linear mixed model on the effect of selected parameters on cover crop emission factors

	F-value	p-value
Constant term	217.642	<0.001
Cover crop diversity	0.840	0.377
Amendments	3.905	0.049
Tillage system	0.903	0.361
Soil type	0.552	0.472
Aridity class	2.096	0.173
Climatic zone	6.167	0.029

Because climatic zone showed a higher significance based on the p-value, we analysed relative EFs (the mean plus the standard error is given below) estimated for the following climatic zones:

- Atlantic = 1.05 (0.014)
- Continental = 1.07 (0.034)
- Mediterranean = 1.08 (0.025)

Figure 4-4: The distribution of relative cover crop emission factors across different soil amendments (Inorganic, N=16; Organic, N=5) and climatic zones (Atlantic, N=10; Continental, N=11; Mediterranean, N=4). The dashed lines represent the mean, while the solid line represents the median.

When conducting a post-hoc test the EF factors of the different climatic zones did not show significant differences ($F=0.211$, $p=0.811$), most probably because the median and average are quite different for two of the three zones.

4.4. Discussion

Overall, the estimated EFs and sequestration rates correspond well with existing literature (Poeplau and Don, 2015). Our analyses suggest that climatic parameters are stronger predictors for relative EFs as compared to soil type or management factors on the European scale. But the data foundation is not satisfactory. There are only a few LTEs that evaluate the sole effect of cover cropping. With an average experimental duration of ca. 11 years, we also lack a comprehensive understanding of the long-term effects (>20 years) of cover cropping. Moreover, the spatial distribution of LTEs across biomes is strongly biased. Although we acknowledge the environmental boundaries of cover cropping, LTEs in many climatic zones, particularly Boreal and Mediterranean regions, are underrepresented. The same applies for soil

types, which were dominated by loamy soils. We urge for more studies across Europe covering a higher diversity of climatic zones and soils.

4.5. Conclusion – Proposed emission factors

Because of the above-mentioned reasons and because the post-hoc test did not show significant differences between climate zones, we recommend using one general EF for cover crops for Europe, i.e., **1.06 (± 0.02)** until more field evidence can show significant differences based on pedo-climatic or management predictors.

5. Crops and crop diversification

Ioanna Panagea¹, Paul Quataert¹, Claudia Di Bene², Greet Ruyschaert¹

¹ Plant Sciences Unit, Flanders research institute for agriculture, fisheries and food (ILVO), 9820 Merelbeke, Belgium

² Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Research Center for Agriculture and Environment, 00184 Rome, Italy

5.1. Introduction

Crop diversification is the practice of diversifying crops either temporally or spatially, which can be achieved through rotation, multiple cropping, or intercropping. Rotation involves cyclically growing a sequence of different crop species on the same land, following a defined order of crop succession (Farina et al., 2018; Karlen et al., 1994; Leteinturier et al., 2006). Multiple cropping refers to growing multiple crop types on the same land within a year, while intercropping involves growing multiple crop types in close proximity to each other. (Azam-Ali, 2003; Francis and Porter, 2017). Crop diversification practices can include higher crop diversity, inclusion of legumes (Pelzer et al., 2017), growing more perennial crops (spatially or/and temporally), implementing temporal grassland (ley-crop-rotations), cultivating minor crops and varieties of local interest (Hufnagel et al., 2020) and/or mixed cropping.

Crop diversification practices are expected to improve the productivity, yield stability, and resource use efficiency (Tamburini et al., 2020). Furthermore, these practices can increase the soil biological activity, reduce the use of pesticides and fertilizers and deliver several ecosystem services including the sequestration of atmospheric C (Beillouin et al., 2019; Di Bene et al., 2022; Garbach et al., 2017; Kremen et al., 2012; Wezel et al., 2014). Crop diversification practices that are expected to incorporate more C into plant biomass that may subsequently increase SOC stocks via increased C inputs, can be diverse, and include higher crop diversity, more perennial crops or temporal grassland (ley-crop-rotations).

Despite the large scientific consensus on the potential agroecological and socio-economic benefits of crop diversification practices, the agronomic solutions for crop diversification strategies are not always economically feasible due to various barriers, linked to the functioning of the dominant agro-food chains (Iocola et al., 2020).

In this Chapter, three objectives have been in the focus: 1) assessing the impact of changes in crop types on the potential for increasing SOC stocks, 2) quantifying this potential by estimating EFs, and 3) identifying factors that affect these EFs. To achieve this, we extracted data from LTEs with different crop rotations from the CarboSeq crop and soil management database. This resulted in a wide variety of (control) treatments that were clustered into the following categories: increased share of legumes, increased share of cereal crops, increased share of root crops, monoculture (i.e., growing of a single crop on the land) versus rotation and rotations with and without temporary leys. The selection of categories to analyse further was based on (1) their potential to increase the SOC stocks, (2) the availability of adequate number of existing LTEs in Europe and (3) the importance for reaching EU policy goals. The option to increase the share of legumes in the rotation after an initial analysis of all the available data from the several

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LTEs covering the majority of the pedoclimatic conditions in Europe showed that has the potential to increase the SOC stocks and is high enough in the political agenda of the EU (European Commission COM(2020) 381, 2020). Thus, this option was selected for further analysis.

Legumes, the main protein crops worldwide and a major source of plant protein play a key role in human and animal nutrition. In addition, they contribute to crop diversification and sustainable farm intensification and further to environmental sustainability due to their ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen. Growing legumes in crop rotations or intercropping provides numerous agronomic and environmental benefits, such as reducing the need for chemical nitrogen fertilizers, improving soil nitrogen content, potentially increasing farmers' income, and reducing the import of legumes when locally produced. However, they also increase the complexity of cropping systems, create a risk of species competition when used for intercropping, and require more labour and technical equipment (knowledge, technical equipment, market access) (Voisin et al., 2014; Wezel et al., 2014).

In Europe, legumes are growing only on 3% of the arable land covering 30% of the EU's crop protein consumption (Häusling, 2011). The eminent lack of protein crops for human and animal consumption coupled with the increasing demand for crop protein, makes European countries highly dependent on imports. To reduce these imports, there is still large potential to increase legumes in the crop rotation, even when livestock numbers would not increase. As a result, Europe is investing in increasing and reintroducing high-protein crops (European Commission, 2018) in its territory by “fostering EU-grown plant proteins” (European Commission COM(2020) 381, 2020) and by “developing a protein plan that will seek to reduce the demand and importation dependency for feed protein crops” (e.g. soya grown on deforested land) as part of the sustainability-based initiatives such as the “EU green Deal” and the “Farm to fork strategy”.

Therefore, in this study, we will demonstrate the effect of increasing leguminous crops in the rotation on SOC stocks by calculating EFs based on data from LTEs in Europe and investigating what environmental and management factors affect these EFs.

5.2. Methodology

Data from the CarboSeq crop and soil management database (version: 2022_11_16, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8130161, <https://zenodo.org/record/8130161>) were extracted following one main prerequisite, i.e., that the only difference between the control treatment and the treatment is the rotation system applied and any other factor (fertilization, organic inputs, tillage etc.) remains the same. 128 entries were identified in the CarboSeq crop and soil management database that were potentially relevant to crop rotation and diversification. After manually checking each entry, and removal of duplicates, 35 experiments were considered to be relevant to the topic of crop rotation and crop diversification. They all included treatments with different rotations, necessary data for analysis (measured SOC stocks or content) and had

a duration of more than 5 years. From these 35 experiments, 28 experiments were found to be relevant for the category about increased share of legumes in the rotation (treatments with different share of legumes in the rotation or conversion to legumes monoculture). Apart from data derived from the CarboSeq crop and soil management database, the following query was used to search for additional published literature testing the completeness of the database using Web of Science in October 2022.

“TS=(soil AND (arable OR agricult* OR farm* OR crop*) AND (legume\$ OR pulse\$ OR alfalfa\$ OR lupin\$ OR lucerne\$ OR bean\$ OR pea\$ OR clover OR soy OR soybean\$ OR perennial\$ OR ley\$ OR permaculture OR rotation OR monoculture OR “mono culture”) AND (“soil organic carbon” OR “soil carbon” OR “soil C” OR “soil organic C” OR SOC OR “carbon pool” OR “carbon stock” OR “carbon storage” OR “soil organic matter” OR SOM OR “carbon sequestrat*” OR “C sequestrat*”) AND (Europe* OR Hungary OR Austria OR Switzerland OR Germany OR Bulgaria OR “United Kingdom” OR UK OR France OR Montenegro OR Luxembourg OR Italy OR Denmark OR Finland OR Slovakia OR Norway OR Ireland OR Spain OR Malta OR Croatia OR Moldova OR Monaco OR Liechtenstein OR Poland OR Iceland OR Albania OR Lithuania OR Slovenia OR Romania OR Latvia OR Netherlands OR Estonia OR Belgium OR “Czech Republic” OR Greece OR Portugal OR Sweden OR Turkey OR Malta OR Cyprus OR Luxembourg)”*

This returned 1026 results. All search results were manually assessed for their relevance to the objectives of our study by checking of the title and abstract. After removing all duplicates that had already been compiled in the CarboSeq crop and soil management database as well as removal of studies that were irrelevant, 103 results were evaluated by checking the full text. After that, four more experiments could be added to the CarboSeq crop and soil management database and were subsequently used in the analysis. Finally, the dataset related to the increased share of legumes in the rotation included 32 experiments with 72 pairs of control and treatment.

Table 5-1: Identified and included experiments in the CarboSeq crop and soil management database. With green it is marked for which category there are possibly relevant pairs of control and treatment within each experiment.

Experiment ID in CarboSeq crop and soil management database	Country	Start	Rotations with and without legumes	With and without ley	Increased part of cereals in rotation	Rotations with and without root crops	Monoculture vs rotation
Gross-Enzersdorf	Austria	1906					
Raasdorf	Austria	1996					
Melle2	Belgium	1966					
KUNZO13V59.1	Czech Republic	1955					
CENTS Flakkebjerg	Denmark	2002					
CENTS Foulum	Denmark	2002					
CHRIS90V94.1	Denmark	1956					
CROPSYS_Flakkebjerg	Denmark	1997					
CROPSYS_Foulum	Denmark	1997					
O_Ler	Denmark	1956					
U_Sand	Denmark	1956					

GLBR	France	2003					
ELMME02V48.1	Germany	1937					
Harste	Germany	2006					
Ihinger Hof	Germany	1976					
rot_Etzdorf	Germany	1970					
Trier	Germany	2011					
10_CREA experimental farm Manfredini	Italy	1994					
3_CREA experimental farm Manfredini	Italy	1992					
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	Italy	1990					
Crop rotation experiment (CR)	Italy	1962					
GRIGN07V26.1	Italy	1993					
Lodi - POC	Italy	1995					
MASCOT	Italy	2001					
PERUC97V24.1	Italy	1971					
Pietranera	Italy	1991					
Kaltinenai	Lithuania	1982					
Apelsvoll	Norway	1989					
Experimental farm near Ås Rotation & Fertilization	Norway	1953					
RYCHC06V52.1	Poland	1967					
Folha 4 S da EAV	Portugal	1997					
43_EEAD Experimental Station	Spain	1989					
El Encin	Spain	1985					
INIA-LTE-ROT	Spain	1994					
Malagon	Spain	1986					
Torrepadierne	Spain	1994					
ZUAZO20	Spain	1950					
La	Sweden	1981					
Lö	Sweden	1981					
Rö	Sweden	1980					

These experiments were further analysed and different crop diversification options using legumes identified: i.e., treatments in which the share of legumes increased within the rotation, treatments where the cropping system converted to monoculture of legumes and treatments where the legume were used as intercrop in orchards. The latter option was not included in the analysis due to sparse data availability (only five pairs from two experiments in the same climatic zone i.e., Mediterranean). To compare rotations with different shares of legumes, the percentage difference of legumes in the treatment compared to the control was determined. For example, if the control treatment was a four-year rotation with legumes present only for

one year (25%) while the treatment was a four-year rotation with 3 years presence of legumes (75%) the percentage difference between both is 50%.

Then, the type of legumes and the growth duration was evaluated. The leguminous crops were separated in grain legumes i.e., those that are cultivated for their grains (e.g., fava beans, soya beans, chickpeas etc.) and in forage legumes i.e., those that are cultivated for their entire above-ground plant parts (e.g., clovers, alfalfa, vetch etc.). The growth duration of the crop was distinguished in annual and multiannual. In treatments where the leguminous crop is planted every year the growth duration is considered as annual, while in treatments where the crop is planted once and remains in the field for more than one year the growth duration is considered as multiannual. Treatments where the crop remains in the field for more than five years were also excluded as according to the EUROSTAT glossary (EUROSTAT, 2018) they are considered to be grasslands.

The EFs calculation was based on the methodology presented in Chapter 3 considering the treatment with the lower share of legumes in the rotation as control.

To identify important predictors for the EFs, LMM were used. The climate, soil and management variables constitute the fixed effects while the experiment ID was introduced as a random effect to account for the within experiment variability, as several pairs of control and treatment were included in each experiment. We used backward stepwise elimination to find the simplest model that explains the data. The final model was fitted using restricted maximum likelihood estimation.

5.3. Results

Estimation of SOC stocks for all treatments based on the available data

First, it was evaluated what the impact is on the calculated EFs if we do not have data for BD and thus if the BD needs to be estimated with a PTF. The PTF makes use of soil texture, so we have also evaluated the influence of using the LUCAS soil dataset to estimate soil texture when soil texture was not available to be used in the PTF. To evaluate this, we selected the pairs for which measured BD was available and also estimated the BD with the PTF and the LUCAS soil data. As shown in Figure 5-1 the EFs are not significantly affected when using the PTF or the textural characteristics of the LUCAS dataset when compared to the measured values of BD and texture.

Figure 5-1: Relationship of EF calculated using measured BD with EF calculated using BD estimated with the PTF and the LUCAS textural characteristics.

As there is no noticeable effect of the use of the PTF or the LUCAS dataset, the complete dataset of EFs was created using the following rules: if possible measured values were used (SOC stocks or SOC concentrations plus measured BD), when the BD was not available, the EF was estimated based on the PTF and measured texture and finally where no textural data nor BD measurements existed the estimated EF was based on the PTF and LUCAS texture to complete the dataset.

Data exploration and selection of final dataset

By exploring the data, it was observed that including grain legumes or forage legumes in the rotation has a different effect on the EFs and SOC storage. Increasing the share of forage legumes in the rotation leads to an increase in SOC and thus positive relative EFs in contrast to the inclusion of grain legumes (Figure 5-2). The relative EFs of the forage legumes and grain legumes are significantly different from each other ($p=0.00027$). Thus, the pairs containing information on grain legumes ($n=28$) were excluded from the analysis, as it could be shown that they do not have the potential to increase the SOC stocks and are thus considered irrelevant to the overall aim of this study.

Figure 5-2: Relative emission factors in relationship with the percentage difference of legumes in the treatment compared to the control. The left panel shows the treatments where the legumes were planted annually while in the right panel the treatments in which the legumes were planted once and remained in the field for more than one year. Within each panel the yellow colour represents the grain legumes and the green colour the forage legumes.

The final dataset used for further analysis includes 21 experiments located in 9 different countries with 39 pairs of treatments and control (i.e., 9 in Italy, 7 in Spain, 5 in Czech Republic, 5 in Denmark, 4 in Germany, 3 in Norway, 3 in Sweden, 2 in Belgium, and 1 in Lithuania) (Figure 5-4). In the treatment of these pairs the share of forage legumes increased within the rotation. In 29 treatments the legumes were planted once and stayed in the field for more than one year and up to 4 years, while in 10 treatments the legumes were planted annually.

The different forage legumes used are alfalfa (15 treatments), vetches (7 treatments), and different clover species or mixtures of clovers with other legumes or grasses (15 treatments) (Figure 5-3). These are planted in the different treatments either as main annual crops in the rotation or/and as intercrops or as main crops in temporary leys (duration 1-4 years) or as mixtures in the grass used in the temporary leys. The forage legumes either replaced other crop types such as cereals (in 16 treatments) or root crops in (4 treatments) (Figure 5-3) or are used as extra crops in the rotation without replacing an existing crop (expansion of the rotation) (14 treatments).

Legumes used in the different treatments

Crop types that replaced by legumes

Figure 5-3: Number of different legume types that used in the different treatments (left) and combinations of crop conversion types (right). The numbers correspond to the numbers of the different treatments in which each case is applied.

Figure 5-4: Spatial distribution of selected long-term field experiments in Europe

The distribution of main climatic and soil type variables is summarized in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2: Number of pairs per country, main climatic zone and USDA soil textural class

Country	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Sandy loam	Loamy sand	Loam	Clay Loam	Silt Loam
Belgium	Atlantic	Humid	2	-	-	-	-
Denmark	Atlantic	Humid	2	1	-	-	-
Lithuania	Boreal	Humid	1	-	-	-	-
Norway	Boreal	Humid	-	-	1	2	-
Sweden	Boreal	Humid	1	-	-	-	1
Czech Republic	Continental	Dry sub-humid	-	-	-	5	-
Germany	Continental	Dry sub-humid	-	-	-	-	2
Denmark	Continental	Humid	2	-	-	-	-
Germany	Continental	Humid	-	-	-	-	2
Italy	Continental	Humid	2	-	6	-	-

Sweden	Continental	Humid	1	-	-	-	-
Spain	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	3	3	-	1	-
Italy	Mediterranean	Humid	-	-	1	-	-

It is observed that the majority of the pairs are in areas with a continental climate (n=20) followed by those in Mediterranean (n=8), the Boreal (n=6) and lastly in Atlantic (n=5) climate zones, raising concerns if conclusions can be drawn for all climatic zones of Europe (apart from the Continental).

The summary of the range of the data in the dataset is presented in Table 5-3 and the distribution of the main variables evaluated in Figure 5-5.

Table 5-3: Summary of the different variables in the selected dataset

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median
Sampling depth (cm)	10	30	23.2	20
Experiment duration (years)	5.0	55.0	28.2	29.0
SOC stock of the control (Mg ha ⁻¹)	11.43	88.49	42.45	39.24
SOC stock of the treatment (Mg ha ⁻¹)	20.71	88.65	44.16	39.82
SOC stock of the control (Mg ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	0.57	3.69	1.86	1.64
Clay content (%)	3.1	24.6	16.0	15.0
Annual precipitation (mm)	428	880	668	775
Annual mean temperature (°C)	3.1	14.2	10.0	9.2
Average aridity index	0.28	1.23	0.75	0.74
Relative EF	0.74	1.89	1.08	1.03

Figure 5-5: Frequency distribution for basic variables in the selected dataset (n=39)

Most of the variables are well distributed based on a visual inspection of normality with the sampling depth to deviate seriously from the normal distribution. Because of that, the SOC stocks were also expressed as SOC stock per cm (by dividing the SOC stocks with the corresponding sampling depth), to account for possible impacts of the sampling depth.

Relative emission factors

The observed relative EFs of the forage legumes ranged between 0.74-1.89 with the average value among all observations to be 1.08 (SE ± 0.03 , SD ± 0.21). The mean EF is significantly higher than 1 (EF = 1 means that the SOC stock of the control is equal to the one of the treatments) as evaluated by a one-way t-test ($p=0.033$).

In this task the difference between the control and the treatments is not binary (e.g., monoculture vs rotation) and the control treatment is not clear. As the selection of pairs occurred based on the share of legumes in the rotation, the percentage difference of legumes between the treatment and the control was kept as constant variable in the models.

The experimental duration and sampling depth, two variables that vary between experiments and can bias the analysis, were considered by conducting a a-priori LMM. The model revealed

that neither experimental duration ($p=0.81$) nor sampling depth ($p=0.17$) had a significant impact on the obtained EF.

To identify important predictors affecting the EF, different variables were considered. These included climate variables (climatic zone, aridity index, aridity class, annual precipitation, mean annual temperature), soil-related variables (clay content, USDA textural class, SOC stock of the control expressed per cm to account for the different sampling depths) and variables related to the management of the crops (crop growth duration of the treatment (annual or multiannual)), percentage difference of legumes in the rotation between the control and the treatment). Before creating the models, these variables were evaluated for correlation and only variables not strongly correlated were included in the same model.

Through backwards elimination and by always including in the models the variable “percentage difference of legumes” the best model was determined which was the one using the predictor variable SOC stock of the control per cm ($p = 0.0032$) and climatic zone ($p = 0.0254$). Significant differences were observed between the Atlantic and Mediterranean climatic zones (Figure 5-6).

Figure 5-6: The distribution of relative emission factors across different climatic zones. The line represents the median value, and the star shows the mean value.

Thus, the **best fitting model** has the following structure:

EF ~ percentage difference + SOC stock of the control per cm + Climatic zone + (1 | Experiment ID)

The summarized results of the model are presented in Table 5-4.

Table 5-4: Optimal model results

	Estimate	Std Error	df	T value	2.5%	97.5%	Pr(> t)
Intercept	1.636388	0.184469	26.877	8.8708	1.265810	1.962679	1.809e-09
percentage difference	0.002432	0.001751	32.998	1.389	-0.000697	0.005826	1.740e-01
SOC of the control per cm	-0.208378	0.064279	26.272	-3.242	-0.323672	-0.074900	3.221e-03
Climatic Zone: Boreal	-0.054360	0.157565	18.186	-0.345	-0.348790	0.224144	7.341e-01
Climatic zone: Continental	-0.319081	0.121926	15.642	-2.617	-0.534794	-0.103868	1.893e-02
Climatic zone: Mediterranean	-0.452892	0.145166	16.122	-3.120	-0.708316	-0.191189	6.552e-03

The final estimated predicted models take the following forms for each climatic zone:

Atlantic: $EF = 1.636388 + 0.002432 * \text{percentage difference} - 0.208378 * \text{SOC of the control per cm}$

Boreal: $EF = 1.582028 + 0.002432 * \text{percentage difference} - 0.208378 * \text{SOC of the control per cm}$

Continental: $EF = 1.317307 + 0.002432 * \text{percentage difference} - 0.208378 * \text{SOC of the control per cm}$

Mediterranean: $EF = 1.183496 + 0.002432 * \text{percentage difference} - 0.208378 * \text{SOC of the control per cm}$

where “percentage differences” refers to additional fraction of fodder legumes in the rotation (%) compared to the control treatment. The range of the predicted EFs relative to the SOC stock of the control expressed per cm for each climatic zone is shown in Figure 5-7 and relative to the percentage difference of legumes between the treatment and the control in Figure 5-8. The higher the SOC stock of the control the lower the potential to increase the SOC stock by increasing the share of forage legumes in the rotation and that a higher percentage of legumes is required. It is observed that the predicted relative EFs are higher when the percentage difference of forage legumes between the treatment and the control is increasing i.e., when forage legumes are included in more years of the rotation, and when the SOC stock of the controls is lower. It is also observed that the highest potential to increase the SOC stock by increasing the percentage of forage legumes in the rotation for a given SOC stock is observed

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in areas in the Atlantic climatic zone followed by those in the Boreal, the Continental and lastly in the Mediterranean climatic zone.

Figure 5-7: Estimated marginal means (predicted values) for the EF relatively to the SOC stock of the control for each climatic zone, when the percentage difference of the legumes between the treatment option and the control option is 25% (red line), 50% (blue line) and 75% (green line) and confidence intervals at 95% level.

Figure 5-8: Estimated marginal means (predicted values) for the EF relatively to the percentage difference of legumes between the treatment option and the control for each climatic zone, when the SOC of the control is 0.5 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (red line), 1.5 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (blue line), 2.5 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (yellow line) and 3.5 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (orange line) and confidence intervals at 95% level.

Considering different scenarios for increased use of forage legumes, the potential change of C stocks based on the control C stocks for each climatic zone is presented in Table 5-5 for a soil depth of 30 cm. It is observed again that with lower SOC of the control, and higher share of the forage legumes in the cropping system the potential to increase the SOC stock is higher. It is also observed that the increased use of forage legumes has a higher potential to increase the SOC stocks in the Atlantic and Boreal climatic zones and a low potential in the Mediterranean.

Table 5-5: Potential change of soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks (Mg/ha) considering different scenarios or initial SOC stock for the 30 cm soil depth and share of forage legumes. Green fields depict an increase in SOC stocks while red shows decrease in SOC stocks.

	Potential change of C stocks (Mg/ha)											
	% more forage legumes in the rotation											
	25%	50%	75%	25%	50%	75%	25%	50%	75%	25%	50%	75%
C stock control (Mg/ha)	Atlantic			Boreal			Continental			Mediterranean		
20 (≈0.5%)	11.2	12.4	13.6	10.1	11.3	12.5	4.8	6.0	7.2	2.1	3.3	4.5
40 (≈1%)	16.8	19.2	21.6	14.6	17.0	19.5	4.0	6.4	8.9	-1.3	1.1	3.5
60 (≈1.5%)	16.8	20.5	24.1	13.6	17.2	20.9	-2.3	1.3	5.0	-10.3	-6.7	-3.1

80 ($\approx 2.0\%$)	11.3	16.2	21.0	7.0	11.8	16.7	-14.2	-9.3	-4.5	-24.9	-20.0	-15.2
105 ($\approx 2.6\%$)	-3.4	3.0	9.4	-9.1	-2.7	3.7	-36.9	-30.5	-24.1	-50.9	-44.5	-38.2

Nevertheless, it was observed that the distribution of available data is not balanced among and within the different climatic zones apart from the Continental climatic zone. For example, in the Mediterranean climatic zone measured data are available only for SOC stocks up to 1.45 Mg/ha/cm while they are only above 2.3 Mg/ha/cm in the Boreal climatic zone. This can happen because in these climatic zones these are the common SOC stock observed but also because of the practices applied (e.g., in the boreal zone we only have rotations with several years of continuous leys).

In this case, the use of a simpler prediction model that does not consider the different climatic zones is recommended.

Thus, the **selected model** has the following structure:

$EF \sim \text{percentage difference} + \text{SOC stock of the control per cm} + (1 | \text{Experiment ID})$

The summarized results of the model are presented in Table 5-6.

Table 5-6: Selected model results

	Estimate	Std Error	df	T value	2.5%	97.5%	Pr(> t)
Intercept	1.182198	0.140086	27.949	8.439	0.888372	1.483102	3.591e-09
percentage difference	0.003957	0.001869	35.904	2.118	0.000321	0.007825	0.04118
SOC of the control per cm	-0.129105	0.050609	23.597	-2.551	-0.236804	-0.027225	0.01766

The final estimated prediction model takes on the following form:

$EF = 1.182198 + 0.003957 * \text{percentage difference} - 0.129105 * \text{SOC of the control per cm}$

The range of the predicted EFs relatively to the percentage difference of legumes between the treatment and the control is shown on Figure 5-9 and the range of the predicted EFs relatively to the SOC stock of the control expressed per cm on Figure 5-10. It is observed that the predicted relative EFs are increasing when the percentage difference of forage legumes between the treatment and the control is increasing i.e., when forage legumes are included in more years of the rotation, and when the SOC stock of the controls is lower. So, the higher the SOC stock of the control the lower the potential to increase the SOC stock by increasing the share of forage legumes in the rotation. It is also observed that in case that the SOC stock of the control is higher than 2 Mg ha⁻¹cm⁻¹ (which is about 60 Mg ha⁻¹ for a soil depth of 30 cm) the predicted relative EFs can be lower than 1 especially when the forage legumes are not present in multiple years in the rotation compared to the control treatment.

Figure 5-9: Estimated marginal means (predicted values) for the EF relatively to the percentage difference of legumes between the treatment option and the control, when the SOC of the control is 0.5 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (red line), 1.5 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (blue line), 2.5 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (yellow line) and 3.5 Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (orange line) and confidence intervals at 95% level.

Figure 5-10: Estimated marginal means (predicted values) for the EF relatively to the SOC stock of the control, when the percentage difference of the legumes between the treatment option and the control option is 25% (red line), 50% (blue line) and 75% (green line) and confidence intervals at 95% level.

Considering different scenarios for increased use of forage legumes, the potential change of C stocks based on the control C stocks is presented in Table 5-7 for a soil depth of 30 cm

For example, in a 4-year rotation which only includes cereal crops, forage legumes will be added in the system for one year (25% increase) or for three years (75% increase) in a soil with about 1% SOC (40 Mg/ha) before legume introduction which represents the mean SOC content of the used dataset. It is shown that there is a potential for increasing the SOC stocks from 4.4 Mg ha⁻¹ at 25 % legumes in the rotation up to 12.3 Mg ha⁻¹ including 75 % legumes, respectively, when applied 28 years on average.

Table 5-7: Potential change of SOC stocks (Mg/ha) considering different scenarios for initial SOC stock and share of forage legumes

C stock control (Mg/ha)	Potential change of C stocks (Mg/ha)		
	% more forage legumes in the rotation		
	25%	50%	75%
20 (≈0.5%)	3.9	5.9	7.9

40 ($\approx 1\%$)	4.4	8.3	12.3
60 ($\approx 1.5\%$)	1.4	7.3	13.2
80 ($\approx 2.0\%$)	-5.1	2.9	10.8
105 ($\approx 2.6\%$)	-17.9	-7.5	2.8

5.4. Discussion

We aimed to identify crop diversification options which have the potential to increase SOC stocks and estimate suitable EFs for the European croplands. Based on the available data, the option to increase the percentage of legumes in the rotation was identified as an option which has the potential to increase the SOC stocks and thus, was evaluated in depth to identify which biophysical and/or management variables control this potential and its magnitude.

Within the treatment option to increase crop diversification by increasing the share of legumes several different crop management options were identified. These included the increase of legumes share both in the rotation and as intercropping (both in arable land and land with permanent tree crops) and the conversion of the control system to monoculture of legumes. At a further step, the type of legumes (grain versus forage legumes) was evaluated. It has been shown by existing research (Whitbread et al., 2000; Young et al., 2009) that the magnitude of C sequestration potential in soils varies among the different leguminous species depending on their total biomass production, their decomposition rates and whether the forage legume is annual or perennial where the potential effects of forage legumes on SOC stock increase seem to be higher with perennial legume species over annual legume crops. The forage legumes, even if used annually, are normally remaining in the field for the entire year in comparison to grain legumes as their cropping season is shorter. Therefore, forage legumes can provide higher C inputs through their rooting system and aboveground biomass in comparison with the annual grain legumes. We demonstrated that it plays a statistically significant role in the potential to increase the SOC stocks if grain or forage legumes are used with the latter to have a potential to increase SOC. Subsequently, the increased share of forage legumes was evaluated.

Forage legumes such as alfalfa, clovers and vetch are used as main annual crops in the rotation or/and as intercrops and, as main crops in temporary leys or as mixtures in the grass used in the temporary leys. Forage legumes have led to an increase in SOC stocks in several ways. First, forage legumes are known to produce more biomass than other forage crops due to their ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen. The resulting increased biomass production can lead to an increased C-input to the soil which is in turn potentially sequestered. The nitrogen fixation capacity also reduces the need for synthetic nitrogen fertilizer, which is energy-intensive to produce and can result in greenhouse gas emissions. By reducing fertilizer use, forage legumes can help to mitigate climate change. Also forage legumes can reduce the need for tillage, especially when are used continuously for more than one year, which can help to reduce soil disturbance and preserve SOC stocks. Overall, forage legumes can be a valuable tool for C sequestration and climate change mitigation, especially in agricultural systems. However, an increase in animal production as consequence of more forage crops would jeopardize the

climate mitigation effects with SOC increase. Both CH₄ and N₂O emissions are related to animal production and comprise a large share of agricultural GHG emissions in Europe. Thus, only the substitution of imported legumes such as soja would be climate positive.

In the experiments evaluated the forage legumes either replaced other crops or were used complementary. The crop type which is replaced and the legume type that is used may influence the C sequestration potential but here, no specific patterns were identified. We considered the number of years when legumes are present both in the control and the treatment option to estimate their percentage difference allowing for comparison.

Using this difference in share of legumes in the complete crop rotation as a constant predictor in our model, reveals that the SOC stock of the control and the climatic zone are statistically significant predictors of the EF and thus we use a regression equation per climatic zone to estimate relevant EF for each specific case. Nevertheless, the data available per climatic zone are imbalanced and may result in poor model performance and bias or even hamper interpretation of the results. Thus, a simpler model which considers only the SOC stock of the control per cm is proposed moving forward.

When the model is used to derive EFs and one intends to interpret the obtained results the assumptions and data limitations caused by the LTEs should always be considered. In the analysis, experiments with different duration are considered and it is assumed that the obtained EFs are valid for a management option in the average experiment duration (i.e., in the field where the management option was applied after x years (average duration) the EF will take the value as estimated with the specific dataset.). Also, the sampling depths vary among the experiments (even if the effect of sampling depth was found to be insignificant with a-priori LMM). To diminish the possible effect of sampling depth on the SOC stocks, the SOC stock of the control that was used as an explanatory variable in the models was expressed per cm, hypothesizing that within the sampling soil layer the SOC is equally distributed and not stratified.

5.5. Conclusion – Proposed emission factors

After considering the different conditions and data limitations, the following regression equation is proposed for the estimation of EFs in the case of having an increased share of forage legumes in the cropping system:

$$EF = 1.182198 + 0.003957 * \text{percentage difference (\%)} - 0.129105 * \text{SOC of the control per cm (Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}\text{)}$$

where “percentage difference” refers to additional fraction of fodder legumes in the rotation (%) compared to the control treatment. The SOC of the control (Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹) is estimated by dividing the SOC of the control with the sampling depth.

The model was estimated based on a set of 21 existing LTEs in different areas and climatic regions in Europe with different inherent soil properties. The use of the proposed model

outside of the soil property ranges and climatic conditions should always be judicious as this model has not been calibrated for this and obtained values should be used with caution.

6. Crop residues

Sophia Götzinger¹, Lisa Makoschitz¹, Taru Sandén¹, Claudia Di Bene², Heide Spiegel¹

¹ AGES - Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety, Department for Soil Health and Plant Nutrition, Vienna

² CREA—Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Research Center for Agriculture and Environment, 00184 Rome, Italy

6.1. Introduction

Soils need a constant addition of organic matter to compensate for C losses from mineralisation processes and for obtaining higher SOC content the C additions need to be higher than the losses. One way to do so is by the addition of exogenous organic matter, such as organic fertilisers and amendments, the other way is by increasing C inputs from biomass that is already grown onsite. Crops add C to the soil via roots, root exudates, stubble and residues of above-ground biomass that is left on the field after harvest (crop residues). If these crop residues such as cereal straw are removed from a field, e.g., for thermal energy production, animal feeding or bedding and not returned, this source of organic C is lost for this specific field. Therefore, we investigated how much the SOC stocks could increase in agricultural soils when crop residues, that are usually are removed, remained on the field, as opposed to fields where they were completely removed.

In addition, retaining above-ground crop residues on fields has been shown to improve soil structure, reduce BD and improve the infiltration rate in soils (Tiefenbacher et al., 2021). Further, when crop residues are left on the soil surface as mulch, they can decrease erosion and reduce evaporation. However, crop residue incorporation can increase the emission of greenhouse gases like N₂O and CO₂ (Lehtinen et al., 2014).

Residues from different crop types contribute different amounts of organic C. The ratio between C and nitrogen (N) in the residues influences SOC as well. The residues of plants with a higher C:N ratio, like maize or cereals, have been shown to build up more C than those of plants with lower C:N ratio, such as legumes (Chen et al., 2018).

Other factors like temperature, clay content and duration of the management practice have been shown to influence the effect of crop residues on SOC stocks (Lehtinen et al., 2014) as well. The aim of this study was to evaluate the long-term C sequestration potential by retaining crop residues on the field versus completely removing them in European agro-ecosystems.

6.2. Methodology

Experiments over Europe were chosen that compare treatments where crop residues had been removed against those where crop residues had been retained and incorporated, for at least consecutive 5 years (Figure 6-1). When other factors were investigated in the experiments, only results from the treatments with fertilizer doses that are common in practice, as well as those plots that had been ploughed regularly were considered for the analysis. The most recent

available data for SOC content was used for the calculation of the relative EFs. A total of 38 experiments could be extracted from the CarboSeq crop and soil management database (version: 2022_10_24, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8130096; <https://zenodo.org/record/8130096>;).

Figure 6-1: Selected crop residue experiment locations over Europe (red dots)

SOC stocks (Mg ha^{-1}) were calculated for the reported sampling depth (between 10 cm and 40 cm) based on the methodology presented in Section 3. The relative EFs were calculated by dividing the SOC stocks of treatments where crop residues were retained, by those where crop residues were removed.

Multiple linear regression models were used to find significant environmental and management predictors of SOC change. To obtain the best fitting models and predictive values, forward selection of parameters was conducted.

For additional validation of this method and testing/visualizing multicollinearity between independent variables, a correlation matrix (Figure 6-5) was created, and a variance inflation factor (vif) analysis was conducted.

The share of cereals in the crop rotation (%) was calculated by the ratio of cereals cultivated compared to other crops in the time of the duration of the experiment. The factor was

expressed as percentage in the statistical summary tables, however, in further use of the value the decimal value is to be considered.

Crop residues in these long-term field experiments originated from cereals (e.g. spring wheat, winter wheat, spring barley, winter barley, winter rye, maize/corn, triticale and oats) and other crops (e.g. lupines, rapeseed, clover, sugar beet, pea, sunflower, beans (soy, broad, horse, field, faba), potato, mustard (white, yellow, oilseed), winter oil radish, vetch, ryegrass and sorghum) according to the percentage in the crop rotation (%).

6.3. Results

A summary of the minimum, maximum, mean and median values of the data in the dataset is presented in Table 6-1 and the distribution of the main variables evaluated in Figure 6-2 below.

Table 6-1: Summary of selected parameters in this analysis

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median
Sampling depth (cm)	10	40	23.5	21.5
Experiment duration (years)	5.0	60.0	29.5	27.5
SOC stock of the control (Mg ha ⁻¹)	14.74	97.68	45.05	41.45
SOC stock of the control (Mg ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	0.63	4.18	1.99	1.93
Clay content (%)	8.0	43.0	20.2	17.0
Crop rotation cereals (%)	40	100	82.19	100
Annual precipitation (mm)	520	1345	748	725
Annual mean temperature (°C)	3.0	15.6	8.99	9.0
Aridity index	0.33	1.53	0.86	0.79
Relative EF	0.87	1.42	1.09	1.07

Figure 6-2: Distribution of selected parameters in the analysis

To determine if SOC stocks calculated with the PTF (Hollis et al., 2012) are different from SOC stocks derived from measured BD, simple linear regressions were calculated. As shown in Figure

6-3 and Figure 6-4 the use of the PTF functions does not significantly change the results as confirmed by a t-test where the difference of the two variables was not significantly different from zero.

Figure 6-3: Measured SOC-stock of control, compared to SOC-stock of control calculated with PTF

Figure 6-4: Relative emission factors from reported values, compared to relative emission factors from PTF.

The strong significant correlations between measured SOC stocks and SOC stocks calculated by using a PTF to derive BD and the respective EFs were further confirmed by the correlation matrix (Figure 6-5). An additional test using linear regression analysis confirmed further significant correlations between independent variables emerging in the matrix. Due to strong correlations of the Aridity Index with annual rainfall, clay content and SOC of the control, this parameter was not considered as a predictive value in the multiple linear regression analysis.

Figure 6-5: Correlation matrix of independent variables (for multiple regression analysis); significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) are indicated in circles, blue circles indicate positive relations, red circles indicate negative correlations.

Figure 6-6: Linear regressions of significant correlations from the correlation matrix with a correlation coefficient (R) and p -value. SOC stock of control and SOC of control per cm were used.

Significant correlations of potential predictors for subsequent multiple regression were visualized in linear regressions (Figure 6-6) to confirm intercorrelations and eliminations. The Aridity Index (AI) increased with increasing precipitation and SOC stock of the control and decreased with higher clay contents (and likewise exhibited exceeding vif values >5 with manual selection).

In addition, both the EF and the mean annual temperature decreased respectively with increasing SOC of the control per sampling depth – suggesting that the higher the control SOC per cm and the cooler the mean annual temperature the lower is the C sequestration potential. Also, the lowest SOC stock of the control treatment could be detected in the Mediterranean zone, however this result is based on only two observations (see Figure 6-7 below).

Figure 6-7: SOC stocks in the controls (crop residue removal) in different climatic zones

Emission factors

For all observations, the mean EF for retained crop residues was 1.09 (SD \pm 0.12, SE \pm 0.02). The average duration of experiments was 29.5 (SD \pm 14.3) years. However, as shown in Figure 6-8 and Table 6-2: Mean EFs and number of observations grouped by experiment duration for crop residue removal below, the experiment duration did not have a significant effect on the EFs (confirmed by a t-test).

Table 6-2: Mean EFs and number of observations grouped by experiment duration for crop residue removal

Experiment duration	EF	n
< 11 years	1.12 ^a	3
11-20 years	1.10 ^a	7
21-30 years	1.10 ^a	11
31-40 years	1.11 ^a	8
>40 years	1.10 ^a	9

Figure 6-8: Distribution of emission factors, grouped by experiment duration. The number of observations per group is shown above the x-axis. The black line represents the median. Values above the red line represent EF>1 (SOC increase), EF<1 (SOC loss).

Since the climatic zone showed a significant effect on SOC stock and EFs (Table 6-3), the climatic differences were analysed and visualized (see Figure 6-9).

Table 6-3: Results of a linear model on the effect of selected parameters on emission factors from crop residue removal

	F value	Pr(>F)
Climatic zone	4.84	0.003
Crop rotation cereals	5.57	0.03
Depth	4.65	0.04
SOC stock of the control	5.64	0.03

Figure 6-9: Distribution of emission factors, grouped by climatic zone. The number of observations per group is shown above the x-axis. The line represents the median.

A Tukey HSD test (post hoc) resulted in three significantly different EFs between Mediterranean-Atlantic ($p=0.03$), Mediterranean-Boreal ($p=0.02$) and Mediterranean-Continental ($p=0.004$) climate zones. However, since there are only two observations for the Mediterranean climatic zone it may not be representative. Mean EFs are seen below (Table 6-4).

Table 6-4: Mean emission factors and number of observations grouped by climatic zone

Climatic zone	EF	n
Alpine	1.13 ^{ab}	1
Atlantic	1.10 ^b	10
Boreal	1.08 ^b	9

Continental	1.04 ^b	12
Mediterranean	1.37 ^a	2
Pannonian	1.12 ^{ab}	2

The proportion of cereals in the crop rotation has also been shown to have a significant effect on EFs. As shown in Figure 6-10 and Table 6-5 below, significant differences are found between 75 - <100 % and 100% (p=0.04) of cereals share in the crop rotation as well as 75 - <100 % and 50 - <75 % (p=0.0004). Since the category of share of cereals in the rotation of < 50 % includes only one observation/experiment, this class could be neglected. The highest mean C sequestration potential was observed in the crop rotation management with 75 - <100 % of cereals.

Figure 6-10: Distribution of emission factors, grouped by number of cereals in the crop rotation. The number of observations per group is shown above the x-axis. The black line inside the boxplots represents the median.

Table 6-5: Mean emission factors and number of observations grouped by % of cereal in the crop rotation

Crop rotation	EF	n
< 50% cereals	0.99 ^b	1
50 - <75% cereals	0.99 ^b	10
75 - <100% cereals	1.22 ^a	6
100% cereals	1.10 ^b	20

The same boxplot and procedure were repeated considering only two crop rotation classes of < 75 % and > 75 % cereals in the rotation (Figure 6-11). The figure shows a significant difference between these two classes (a crop rotation class with more than 75 % cereals in the rotation has a significantly higher EF, i.e., a greater C sequestration potential).

Figure 6-11: Distribution of emission factors, grouped by <75 % and >75% of cereals in the crop rotation. The number of observations per group is shown above the x-axis. The black line inside the boxplots represents the median.

Table 6-6: Mean emission factors and number of observations grouped by < 75 % and > 75 % of cereal in the crop rotation

Crop rotation	EF	n
< 75% cereals	0.99 ^b	11
> 75% cereals	1.12 ^a	26

Predictive formulas

Two different regression models were tested using different approaches and predictors. The considered predictors in this study were clay content (%), SOC per sampling depth of the control treatment ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), duration of the experiment (years), annual rainfall (mm), mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), and share of cereals in crop rotation.

The first model was determined by stepwise regression (a combination of forward and backward selection). The resulting best model includes clay content (%), SOC per cm (control treatment) ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), annual rainfall (mm), and cereals in crop rotation as predictors (AIC=-53.78, BIC=-44.63, $p=0.002$). The corresponding formula is as follows:

$$\text{EF} = 1.1145603004 + 0.0029884854 * (\text{Clay}) - 0.0757464623 (\text{SOC stock/depth}) - 0.0001467569 * (\text{annual rainfall}) + 0.2146727314 * (\text{crop rotation}) \quad (\text{Multiple } R^2: 0.44, p=0.002).$$

Table 6-7: Results of a linear model (stepwise selection) for the effect of selected parameters on emission factors

	F value	Pr(>F)	Pr(>t)
Clay	3.56	0.07	0.13
SOC stocks of control per sampling depth	11.61	0.002**	0.001**
Annual rainfall	1.92	0.18	0.18
Crop rotation	5.66	0.02 *	0.01*

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

The most significant predictors are SOC stocks per sampling depth as well as crop rotation with $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$ respectively.

Table 6-8: Results of the best fitting model

	Estimate	Std Error	df	t value	2.5%	97.5%	Pr(> t)
Intercept	1.1145603	0.1091438	1	10.212	0.8913362660	1.337784e+00	4.09e-11
SOC control per cm	-0.0757465	0.0208731	1	-3.629	-0.1184367481	-3.305618e-02	0.00108
Crop rotation	0.2146727	0.0821768	1	2.612	0.0466022114	3.827433e-01	0.01410
Clay content	0.0029885	0.0019218	1	1.555	-0.0009419906	6.918961e-03	0.13078
Annual rainfall	-0.0001468	0.0001060	1	-1.385	-0.0003635236	7.000984e-05	0.17671

Based on previous results where SOC per sampling depth and crop rotation had the most significant impact on the EF, another model run was performed using only these two as predictors (as numbers). A simple linear regression was performed and resulted in following equation:

$$\text{EF} = 1.08264 - 0.07443 * (\text{SOC of control per depth}) + 0.18457 * (\text{crop rotation}) \quad (R^2=0.3416, p=0.001011)$$

The summary of the model can be seen in Table 6-9 below.

Table 6-9: Results of the model with SOC of control per cm and amount of cereals in crop rotation (as numbers)

	Estimate	Std Error	df	t value	2.5%	97.5%	Pr(> t)	F value
Intercept	1.08264	0.07604	1	14.239	0.92794094	1.23732974	1.2e-15	
SOC control per cm	-0.07443	0.02057	1	-3.617	-0.11628422	-0.03256674	0.000982	11.81
Crop rotation	0.18457	0.08003	1	2.306	0.02173696	0.34739745	0.027526	5.32

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

By including the two rotation classes as a factor following results were obtained:

EF = 1.13316 - 0.06933 * (SOC of control per cm) + 0.12982 * (rotation with >75% cereals - decimal) (AIC=-66.05, BIC=-59.71).

This model explained 48% of the variability of the EF (p= 1.895e-05).

The summary can be seen in the tables below.

Table 6-10: Summary of F-value and Pr(>F) for the prediction model with SOC of control per cm and Crop rotation class >75% cereals as predictors.

	F value	Pr(>F)
SOC control per cm	15.024	0.0004777***
Rotation class >75% cereals	15.761	0.0003663***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Table 6-11: Results of the model with SOC of control per cm and amount of cereals in crop rotation (as factors)

	Estimate	Std Error	df	t value	2.5%	97.5%	Pr(> t)
Intercept	1.13316	0.04547	1	24.920	1.04064843	1.22567386	< 2e-16
SOC control per cm	-0.06933	0.01818	1	-3.815	-0.10631400	-0.03235375	0.000568
Rotation class > 75% cereals	0.12982	0.03270	1	3.970	0.06329329	0.19635509	0.000366

Table 6-12: Summary of multiple regression models with R², p, predictors and their significance and formulas

Model	Predictors	R ² and p-value
Forward selection	SOC control per cm ** Crop rotation* Clay content Annual rainfall	Multiple= 0.4397 Adjusted = 0.3624 p=0.001661

EF = 1.11 - 0.08 * SOC/depth (Mg ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹) + 0.21 * crop rotation cereals (decimal) + 0.003 * Clay (%) - 0.0001 * annual rainfall (mm)		
Multiple linear regression	SOC per sampling depth** crop rotation*	Multiple= 0.3416 Adjusted= 0.3017 p=0.001011
EF = 1.08264 - 0.07443 *(SOC of control per depth) + 0.18457 *(crop rotation)		
Multiple linear regression	SOC per sampling depth*** Rotation class >75% cereals ***	Multiple= 0.4826 Adjusted= 0.4513 p= 1.895e-05
EF = 1.13316 - 0.06933 * (SOC of control per cm) + 0.12982 * (rotation with >75% cereals - decimal)		

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Emission factor per climatic zone

Another regression analysis per climatic zone - for those who had >5 observations was performed considering Continental, Atlantic and Boreal climates to test if there are prediction differences between them. The predictive parameters of the optimal/best fitting model were determined by forward selection (as before).

The model for the continental zone includes the cereal share in the complete crop rotation and SOC content per sampling depth (Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹) as predictors, while the model for the Atlantic zone includes SOC content per sampling depth (SOC Mg ha⁻¹ cm⁻¹), cereal share in the complete crop rotation, experimental duration, annual rainfall (mm) and mean annual temperature (°C). This resulted in the following equations:

$$EF_{\text{continental}} = 0.95 + 0.27 * (\text{crop rotation} - \text{decimal}) - 0.04 * (\text{SOC per cm} - \text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}) \quad (R^2 = 0.52, p = 0.04).$$

The most significant predictor for the $EF_{\text{continental}}$ is the crop rotation ($p < 0.05$).

$$EF_{\text{atlantic}} = 0.76 - 0.05 * (\text{SOC per cm} - \text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}) + 0.37 * (\text{crop rotation} - \text{decimal}) + 0.002 * (\text{Duration} - \text{years}) + 0.00008 * (\text{annual rainfall} - \text{mm}) - 0.006 * (\text{mean annual temperature} - ^\circ\text{C}) \quad (R^2 = 0.98, p = 0.01).$$

The most significant predictors for the EF_{atlantic} are SOC per depth and crop rotation ($p < 0.01$) followed by duration ($p < 0.05$) and annual rainfall ($p < 0.1$). Almost all the EF_{atlantic} data could be explained by this model.

No significant model was obtained for the Boreal zone ($p = 0.21$).

6.4. Discussion

Within this study we calculated an average EF of 1.09 (SD +/- 0.12). However, based on the number of observations per climatic zone we were only able to obtain prediction models for the Continental and Atlantic climatic zone. The average EF for the continental and Atlantic climatic zone are 1.04 (SD +/- 0.11) and 1.10 (SD +/- 0.06) respectively.

As a preliminary analysis to the multiple regression performance (keyword multicollinearity analysis), significant correlations (Figure 6-6) were looked at in more detail. The phenomenon of a negative correlation between clay content and Aridity Index was also documented in another study stating that the clay content is generally higher in wetter/more severe climates due to more active soil rock weathering processes, ion release and clay mineral formation (Zhong et al., 2018). The positive correlation between aridity index and annual rainfall confirms the definition of the index which states that the more humid and wetter the climate and precipitation/rainfall, the higher the AI (Trabucco and Robert, 2018).

Likewise, a positive correlation between SOC stocks and the AI ($R=0.38$) could be seen, which is consistent with findings of Alvarez & Lavado, (1998) and Zhong et al., (2018) who indicate that humid climates favour the increase of SOC stocks.

Similarly, a negative correlation of mean annual temperature (MAT) and SOC stocks ($R=-0.6$) was seen in Figure 6-6, which could be explained by slower decomposition rates and reduced mineralisation of C with decreasing temperatures (Yan et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2017). The reduction in C stocks was found to be greater in coarse-textured soils with limited organic matter stabilization than in fine-textured soils with greater stabilization capacity. Our results were also confirmed by Hartley et al. (2021) who stated that this pattern was observed independently in cool and warm regions.

The decreasing EF with increasing SOC per sampling depth of the control, demonstrates that a new C equilibrium between C inputs and C outputs will be reached where overall SOC stocks are found at a higher level than before.

Moreover, according to the analysis that was carried out, different EFs could be calculated for climatic zones and crop rotations. Table 6-4 and Table 6-5 show mean EFs grouped by climatic zones and crop rotation. However, the fact that some groups only have a low number of reported values needs to be taken into consideration when interpreting these values due to reduced statistical power, sampling bias and increased variability.

The highest EFs and relative changes were found in the Mediterranean climate but is based solely on 2 treatment pairs. Thus, we excluded the Mediterranean EF before computing a mean EF over the remaining climatic zones. Soils in Mediterranean regions tend to be often low in organic matter, and therefore have a SOC sequestration potential, which would be in line these findings.

Furthermore, in this analysis a crop rotation with 75 - <100% cereals resulted in the highest EFs and relative changes (Table 6-5). Although cereals have a high C/N-ratio and biomass production resulting in high quantity and quality of C-inputs to soils, a monoculture of cereals can have negative effects on the plant development - compared to more diverse crop rotations - resulting in lower crop yields and root residues and therefore decrease the total amount of C that can be supplied to the soil (Govaerts et al., 2007). By including crops in a rotation (field and vegetable crops), a positive effect on SOC was documented related to increases in soil microbial biomass and biological activity (McDaniel et al., 2014). The inclusion of one or more crops in a rotation compared to a monoculture increases total organic SOC and N. This means that a cereal share of >75 - <100% cereals in the rotation should be preferred to monoculture (100% cereals).

The 50 - <75% cereal crop rotation had a mean EF of <1, however this was not significant different to EF=1, thus a lower potential for C sequestration in soils compared to the other cereal rotations could not be confirmed.

Crop rotation and SOC stock per depth played a key role in predicting EFs, which is also consistent with findings of G. Zhao et al. (2013) and Stella et al. (2019). In many studies, returning crop residues to the soil was found to be a promising management strategy to mitigate SOC loss/decline in cropping systems (Bolinder et al., 2020; Lehtinen et al., 2014; Tang et al., 2006).

6.5. Conclusion – Proposed emission factors

The values shown in Table 6-4 and Table 6-5 could be used for further analysis for the area of implementation. Taking this study's conditions and limitations into consideration, following regression equation for calculation the EF for crop residue management is proposed:

$$\text{EF} = 1.114560 - 0.075746 * \text{SOC of the control per cm (Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}) + 0.214673 * \text{crop rotation (decimal)} + 0.002988 * \text{Clay content (\%)} - 0.000147 * \text{annual rainfall (mm)}$$

The amount of C potentially sequestered in the soil depends on further physicochemical and management factors. For instance, management practices such as no-till or reduced tillage can help to retain crop residues on soil surfaces, reducing their decomposition rates and increasing their contribution to soil C.

Considering crop residue management many studies suggest that this management alone is unlikely to lead to SOC accumulation, but rather has immediate beneficial effects on soil health and is also dependent previously mentioned factors (Hartley et al., 2021; Stella et al., 2019). The EFs indicate that management systems with retention of residues show higher SOC stocks after a certain number of experimental years than when residues are removed. But it will also depend on other (e.g. weather/climatic/soil) factors and management practices whether SOC stock is decreasing, increasing, or remaining the same in the long-term.

Finally, capturing the influence of crop diversity on EFs may require more LTEs with crop rotations including different fixed proportions of cereals.

7. Tillage

María Alonso-Ayuso¹, Kristina Ocvirk², Laura B. Martinez-Garcia ¹, Marjetka Suhadolc², Jorge Álvaro-Fuentes¹

¹ Spanish National Research Council. Department of Soil and Water, Estación Experimental de Aula Dei, 50015 Zaragoza. Spain.

² University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

7.1. Introduction

The loss of C in agricultural soils has often been assigned to deep tillage or ploughing of the soils. In the last decade, conservation agriculture recommends using less intensive non-inversion tillage practices (minimum or reduced tillage) and no-till or zero tillage (the absence of mechanical soil disturbance) to increase SOC content and improve soil health (Holland, 2004). However, it is often discussed that these management options redistribute the organic matter in the soil profile rather than increasing overall SOC stocks. The most recent review of meta-analyses (Lessmann et al., 2022) confirmed the positive effects of non-inversion tillage practices and zero tillage on SOC stock increase in the upper layer (0-30 cm) finding a positive effect that varied from 0.07 to 0.31 t C ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ in the temperate climatic zone (Angers & Eriksen-Hamel, 2008; Haddaway et al., 2017; Meurer et al., 2018). In this task we aimed to calculate EFs for zero tillage and non-inversion tillage practices based on European LTEs comparing these practices to conventional inversion tillage and disentangle the main factors that determine the relative EFs in the 0 to 30 cm soil layer.

7.2. Methods

Experiments that are running for at least 5 years and comparing conventional inversion tillage with mouldboard ploughing (control) to treatments with other tillage management (either non-inversion tillage or zero-tillage), were included in the analysis. Inversion tillage involves a one-off inversion of agricultural soil to depths of up to 30 cm, while in the non-inversion tillage, the soil is not inverted. Zero tillage represents a management practice in which the soil is never tilled.

Therefore, the data extraction from the CarboSeq crop and soil management database (version: 2022_10_24, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8130096; <https://zenodo.org/record/8130096>;) followed the query: 'Inversion tillage' (control) vs. 'other'. Then, manually, the experiments comparing 'Inversion tillage' (control) vs. 'non-inversion tillage' (treatment) were separated from those comparing 'Inversion tillage' (control) vs. 'Zero-tillage' (treatment). Only experiments with sampling depths up to 30 cm (and sampling depth>10cm) and with a duration longer than 5 years were selected. Only pairs of treatments with the same management – in terms of fertilization, crop rotation or residues management - were included. For experiments with SOC data from different years, only those from the most recent year were used.

7.3. Results

Data exploration

The spatial distribution of the selected LTEs is shown in Figure 7-1 and Figure 7-2 for the non-inversion tillage and zero-tillage management options respectively.

Figure 7-1: Spatial distribution of selected long-term field experiments in Europe with non-inversion treatments

Figure 7-2: Spatial distribution of selected long-term field experiments in Europe with zero-tillage treatments

A summary of the different variables in the tillage dataset used in the analysis is presented in Table 7-1. Overall, the mean experimental duration was approximately 15 years. The majority of zero-tillage experiments were conducted in the Mediterranean climate (14 out of 27), followed by Continental (5 out of 27), Atlantic (5 out of 27), Boreal (2 out of 27) and Pannonian (1 out of 27). Non-inversion tillage practices were primarily studied in Continental climates (25 out of 46), following by Mediterranean (12 out of 46), Atlantic (6 out of 46) and Boreal (3 out of 46). Notably, only one experiment under zero-tillage was conducted in a Pannonian climate, and there were no experiments under non-inversion tillage for this climate type.

The clay content of experiments in both zero tillage and non-inversion tillage covered a wide range, from a few percent to as high as 78%. However, the highest number of experiments belonged to loam and silty loam texture categories. Specifically, for zero-tillage, 7 experiments were in the loam category and 5 in the silty loam category (out of 27 experiments total). For non-inversion tillage, 11 experiments were in the loam category and 12 in the silty loam category (out of 47 experiments total). Only the sandy clay texture class was not represented in either dataset.

Table 7-1: Summary of the variables included in the dataset and in the statistical analysis.

Inversion vs. Non-inversion tillage 47 experiments				
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median

Sampling depth (cm)	15.0	40.0	22.8	20
Experiment duration (years)	5.0	36.0	15.2	15
SOC stock of the control (Mg ha ⁻¹)	4.10	97.68	33.15	29.28
Clay content (%)	2.50	63.80	21.32	16.64
Annual precipitation (mm)	332	1413	764	797
Annual mean temperature (°C)	4.8	18.1	10.5	8.53
Average aridity index	0.21	1.63	0.88	1.08
EF with fixed depth C stocks	0.72	1.54	1.05	1.045
EF with ESM C stocks	0.72	1.43	1.03	1.037

Inversion vs. Zero-Tillage 27 experiments				
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median
Sampling depth (cm)	15.0	30.0	28.4	30
Experiment duration (years)	5.0	28.0	14.3	15
SOC stock of the control (Mg ha ⁻¹)	13.26	99.06	38.07	29.22
Clay content (%)	5.30	78.70	30.05	22.3
Annual precipitation (mm)	332	1164	531	428
Annual mean temperature (°C)	5.8	17.9	14.2	13.9
Average aridity index	0.21	1.40	0.54	0.28
EF with fixed depth C stocks	0.59	1.62	1.14	1.127
EF with ESM C stocks	0.59	1.63	1.11	1.098

Relative emission factors

For the comparison between ‘Inversion tillage’ and ‘Non-inversion tillage’, selection resulted in 46 experiments, whereas for the comparison between ‘Inversion tillage’ and ‘Zero-tillage’, selection resulted in 27 different experiments. It is important to note that the SOC stocks increase or reduction rates due to tillage were estimated using two approaches: (i) the fixed depth approach and (ii) the equivalent soil mass approach (ESM) (see Section 3).

Mean relative EF for both non-inversion and zero-tillage were significantly higher than 1 (Table 7-1; Figure 7-3). The relative EF for zero-tillage was significantly higher compared to non-inversion tillage regardless of the SOC stock calculation approach. For zero-tillage, EF was **1.14 (SD ±0.25)** when SOC stock calculated to a fixed depth, and **1.11 (SD ±0.19)** using the equivalent soil mass approach. For non-inversion tillage, the EF was **1.05 (SD ±0.18)** and **1.03 (SD ±0.12)** when SOC stock calculated to a fixed depth and equivalent soil mass, respectively.

Comparing the two EF calculation approaches, for ‘Non-inversion tillage’, the EF from SOC stocks calculated to a fixed depth were significantly higher compared to the EF from SOC stocks calculated with the equivalent soil mass approach. For ‘Zero-tillage’, the EF were not

significantly different between the two SOC stocks calculation approaches; however, it is of note that there were a higher number of comparisons in 'Non-inversion tillage' than 'Zero-tillage'.

Figure 73: Relative emission factors comparing conventional tillage vs. zero-tillage and conventional tillage and non-inversion tillage (RT) according to calculation approaches. The horizontal lines represent the 0.25 and 0.75 quartiles and the median.

For non-inversion tillage the EF variation is lower compared to zero-tillage (Figure 7-3). However, in both tillage systems, EF variability cannot be attributed to outliers. Besides soil tillage practices, pedo-climatic conditions, other soil management practices, soil sampling biases, bulk density determination, and the method used for EF calculation also influence the variability of EFs among and within experiments. For example, some of the highest EFs in the 'Zero-tillage' dataset are observed in the Mediterranean climates, but the lowest also comes from this region. Specifically, the lowest EF for zero-tillage was recorded at 0.59 using the fixed depth approach in a Spanish experiment on clay loam soil, while EF in the same experiment using the equivalent soil mass approach was 0.97. These variations highlight the complexity of factors influencing EF determinations.

Correlation among the variables that describe soil texture (sand and clay) and variables that are related to climate (MAT, MAP, aridity index, latitude and longitude) were calculated using Pearson correlation coefficients for the zero-tillage and the non-inversion tillage dataset (Table

7-2). For both datasets; latitude was strongly correlated with MAT. Similarly, aridity index was strongly correlated with MAP. Therefore, we excluded latitude and aridity index within the initial model. The other variables were less correlated and were included in the initial model that was used to follow step wise selection.

Table 7-2: R values and p-values of pairwise comparison between variables, non-inversion tillage (upper triangle) and no-till (lower triangle). * p-value<0.5, **p-value<0.01, ***p-value<0.001

		Non-Inversion Tillage						
		Latitude	Longitude	MAT	MAP	Aridity index	Clay	Sand
Zero Tillage	Latitude		0.81***	-0.91***	0.38***	0.68***	-0.38***	0.19**
	Longitude	0.71***		-0.88***	0.54***	0.70***	-0.16*	0.18**
	MAT	-0.93***	-0.70***		-0.60**	-0.81***	0.25	0.04
	MAP	0.47***	0.28**	-0.47***		0.93***	-0.03	-0.9
	Aridity index	0.77***	0.48***	-0.76***	0.90***		-0.19**	-0.02
	Clay	-0.42*	-0.18*	0.52***	-0.10	-0.27**		-0.20**
	Sand	0.26**	0.22	-0.28	0.19*	0.17	-0.51***	

Histogram of the relative EF showed a normal distribution of the data. However, histograms of the groups within categorical variables revealed that for some variables such as USDA soil texture class, climatic zone and aridity class, there is low number of observations and lack of normality in some of the groups. This has to be considered when interpreting the model results.

Stepwise selection started by a model that tested the effect of all the variables that were not correlated and the categorical variables.

$$\text{Relative EF} \sim \text{SOC stock in control} + \text{Climatic zone} + \text{USDA soil type} + \text{Sampling depth} + \text{Experiment duration} + \text{MAT} + \text{MAP} \tag{1}$$

After step wise backward selection for both EF calculation methods (fixed depth and equivalent soil mass), the **best fitting model to predict relative EF with zero-tillage was:**

$$\text{Relative EF} \sim \text{USDA soil type} \tag{2}$$

And for non- inversion tillage:

$$\text{Relative EF} \sim \text{USDA soil type} + \text{Sampling depth} \tag{3}$$

The summarized results of all four models are presented in Table 7-3.

Table 7-3: Parameters of the optimal LME to predict the relative emission factor of zero tillage and non-inversion tillage compared to inversion tillage.

Method	Zero-tillage						
	ANOVA	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	p value
Fixed depth	USDA soil_type_	0.239	0.04	4	4.6036	2.228	0.21

ESM	USDA soil_type	0.187	0.0312	6	5.4294	1.7426	0.27
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Method		Non-inversion tillage					
	ANOVA	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	p value
Fixed depth	USDA soil_type	0.142	0.018	8	2.48	1.49	0.43
	Sampling depth	0.104	0.052	2	3.51	4.42	0.11
ESM	USDA soil type	0.130	0.016	8	2.00	1.18	0.42
	Sampling depth	0.099	0.049	2	5.19	5.72	0.09

USDA soil type and sampling depth were the two main factors determining relative EF under non-inversion tillage and USDA soil type under zero-tillage. However, the effect of these two factors on EF were only marginally significant ($0.05 < p\text{-value} < 1$) for both calculation approaches and both tillage methods. It should be however noted that the texture classes were not equally represented among the experiments in either the zero-tillage or non-inversion tillage datasets (Figure 7-4 and Figure 7-5).

Figure 7-4: EF with fixed depth stocks calculations for non-inversion tillage according to soil texture type. The dashed line represents the suggested EF for non-inversion tillage. Averages with standard errors and number of observations are shown.

Figure 7-5: EF with fixed depth stocks calculations for zero-tillage according to soil texture type. The dashed line represents the suggested EF for zero-tillage. Averages with standard errors and number of observations are shown.

7.4. Discussion

This is the first meta-analysis performed for the entire European cropland surface. Our analysis indicates that both zero tillage and non-inversion tillage have potential for carbon sequestration. Additionally, zero-tillage resulted in higher average EF values compared to non-inversion tillage. Global meta-analyses published have shown positive EFs for zero tillage and non-inversion tillage but only under certain soil and climatic conditions (Ogle et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2020). In particular, greater EF is observed under zero tillage in arid/semiarid areas due to its positive effect on crop production and, thus, C inputs (Pittelkow et al., 2015).

In our analysis, climate exerted a strong bias in the dataset, with unequal representation of all climates among experiments. The highest number of experiments were conducted in Mediterranean climate, especially under zero tillage. Specifically, 14 out of 27 zero-tillage experiments in our dataset were conducted in Mediterranean climate. Moreover, most experiments in Mediterranean climate were in semiarid Spain. In the first meta-analysis done with experiments only from semiarid rainfed Spain, the EF found for zero tillage was 1.22 (Alvaro-Fuentes and Cantero-Martinez, 2010). Our EF for zero-tillage is lower (1.14 (SD ±0.25)),

which is expected due to broader dataset, which beside 14 experiments from Mediterranean Spain, includes also experiments from Continental (5), Atlantic (5), Boreal (2) and Pannonian (1) climates.

Despite the geographical bias towards Mediterranean semiarid type experiments in our data, the resulting EF were comparable to EF estimated in more global assessments, such as the EF from IPCC for zero-tillage (no-till) and non-inversion tillage (reduced tillage), 1.1 and 1.05 respectively (IPCC, 2006). Finally, the two variables that best predict relative EF were USDA soil type soil and sampling depth. However, the effects of these two variables were marginally significant for both tillage systems. The prediction of EF could be improved by expanding the initial database with experiments conducted on less represented soil textures and climates in our data set. Both measures are however well within the goal of the 4 per 1000 initiative.

7.5. Conclusion – Proposed emission factors

Our analysis showed that for zero-tillage, EF is 1.14 (SD ± 0.25) when calculated to a fixed depth and 1.11 (SD ± 0.19) using the equivalent soil mass approach. For non-inversion tillage, the EF is 1.05 (SD ± 0.18) and 1.03 (SD ± 0.12) when calculated to a fixed depth and equivalent soil mass, respectively. Notably, no significant differences between the two calculation approaches were found for zero-tillage, while for non-inversion tillage EF calculated to a fixed depth were significantly higher compared to EF calculated with equivalent soil mass approach. However, the difference is small (1.05 compared to 1.03).

Therefore, for further use, for both tillage practices, we suggest using EF values calculated with a fixed depth and using measured BD for C stock calculation. Specifically, we propose an EF of 1.14 for zero-tillage and an EF of 1.05 for non-inversion tillage, irrespective of pedoclimatic conditions.

8. Irrigation

María Alonso-Ayuso¹, Jorge Álvaro-Fuentes¹,

¹ Spanish National Research Council. Department of Soil and Water, Estación Experimental de Aula Dei, 50015 Zaragoza. Spain

8.1. Introduction

Irrigation influences SOC dynamics via several processes. On the one hand, water supply leads to an increased crop productivity, and therefore leads to a higher input of C into the soil (Entry et al., 2004). On the other hand, a higher soil moisture enhances soil microbial activity, that can increase the decomposition of soil organic matter which may lead to lower SOC stocks (Dersch and Böhm, 2001). Besides, the impact of irrigation may vary with the interaction with other management practices as fertilization or tillage and is strongly dependent on climate (Trost et al., 2013).

Until now, two reviews have explored the impact of irrigation on SOC stocks (Emde et al., 2021; Trost et al., 2013). On the one hand, Trost et al. (2013) collected data from 14 LTEs (> 8 years) and observed the SOC stocks under irrigation compared with non-irrigation. Of them, only two were conducted in Europe (in Germany and Austria), with a duration of 32 and 27 years respectively. Both of them were included in this report. In summary, Trost et al. (2013) observed that under arid conditions with low precipitation and low initial SOC contents, irrigation led to increases in SOC, whereas in arable soils with higher SOC stocks no significant differences were observed between irrigated and non-irrigated plots or slight decreases. But the authors pointed out that in the reviewed publications, other management factors as tillage and fertilisation also varied, so the effects might be a consequence of interaction with those.

On the other hand, Emde et al. (2021) performed a metanalysis of data from studies that examined changes in SOC stocks on irrigated agricultural sites over time (therefore, none of those studies were included in this report). As isolating the effect of irrigation per se on SOC stocks is difficult, they characterized trends in SOC stocks under irrigated agriculture. They observed that irrigated agriculture tends to increase SOC stocks (~6% increase), where the greatest increase was observed in arid to semi-arid climates at the 0-10 cm soil depth.

In this task, it was expected to further search in literature and compile and analyse the results of European LTEs (>5 years) that investigate the impact of irrigation on arable land vs no irrigation on SOC stocks.

8.2. Methods

The results of European LTEs were compiled in the CarboSeq crop and soil management database (version 2022_10_03, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8127976, <https://zenodo.org/record/8127976>) and for the analysis of this chapter, experiments that compared irrigated treatments to those that did not receive irrigation were selected (using the query "non-irrigated" (control) vs. "others"). This resulted in eight experiments. From these, it

was investigated if the duration was at least 5 years or longer and if they had SOC stock measurements for a depth of at least 10 cm. Only three experiments eventually qualified.

8.3. Results

The spatial distribution of the selected LTEs for irrigation is shown in Figure 8-1.

Figure 8-1: Spatial distribution of selected long-term field experiments in Europe

Experiment 1: Germany

The first experiment was carried out on a sandy soil in north-eastern Germany under a dry sub-humid continental climate. In this experiment the combined impact of irrigation and nitrogen fertilizer application (Zero N, Normal N, Excessive N) over a period of 35 years was assessed (Trost et al., 2014). Only the pairs with the same fertilization in the control and in the treatment were used for the comparison (3 pairs, no replicates).

In this case, the mean relative EF was **1.027 (SE ±0.006)**. Therefore, in this experiment, the irrigation showed a positive impact on SOC stocks. As observed in Figure 8-2 the EF value in the pair with no fertilization (Zero N) was slightly higher (1.034) than the EF value obtained in the pair with excessive N application (1.019).

Figure 8-2: Relative emission factors for the three pairs of observations comparing non-irrigated (control) vs. Irrigated (treatment), with different nitrogen fertilizer application.

Experiment 2: Italy

The second experiment was carried out in a sandy clay loam soil located in Italy under semiarid Mediterranean conditions, in which they assessed the combined effect of irrigation and different cereal-forage rotations over a period of 18 years (Martiniello et al., 2012). The different crop rotations evaluated were:

- Three years of BM (beerseem clover, *Trifolium alexandrinum* L. + barley, *Hordeum vulgare* L.) after three years of continuous wheat (1-yr BM, 2-yr BM and 3-yr BM)
- Three years LM (*Medicago sativa* L.) after wheat continuously grown for 3-yr (1-yr LM, 2-yr LM and 3-yr LM)
- Continuous wheat for all period of experiment (CDW)
- 3-yr continuous wheat after a 3-yr continuous BM (1-yr DWBM, 2-yr DWBM, 3-yr DWBM)
- 3-yr continuous wheat after a 3-yr old meadow (1-yr DWLM, 2-yr DWLM and 3-yr DWLM)

In this case, the mean EF for irrigated vs. non-irrigated treatments was **0.90 (SE±0.02)**. This can be explained as, under semiarid conditions, the increase of soil moisture can lead to C losses - because of a higher respiration – that are greater than the C amount increase caused by enhanced growth of biomass (Figure 8-3).

Figure 8-3: Relative emission factors for the thirteen pairs of observations comparing non-irrigated (control) vs. Irrigated (treatment), with different wheat-forage crop rotations. Small bars above the bars indicate the SD.

Experiment 3: Austria

The third experiment was performed on a loam sandy soil in Austria under a dry sub-humid continental climate. Like the German experiment, the combined impact of irrigation and nitrogen fertilizer application over a period of 27 years was assessed (Dersch and Böhm, 2001). In this case, the mean relative EF was **0.95 (SE ±0.011)**.

8.4. Discussion

In the three identified experiments, irrigation showed a positive impact on SOC stocks under one of the experiments performed under a dry-sub humid continental climate, whereas it led to SOC stock losses under a semiarid Mediterranean climate (Figure 8-4).

Figure 8-4: Emission factors in the three experiments comparing rainfed vs irrigated systems. Mean + SE

8.5. Conclusion – Proposed emission factors

To now, there is not enough information to draw robust conclusions about the impact of irrigation on soil SOC stocks. Therefore, more field experiments would be necessary to fill this gap. Based on the current field evidence, we cannot propose meaningful EFs nor irrigation as a C sequestration measure.

9. Agroforestry

Sonja Kay¹, Valerie Viaud², Sophie Drexler³

¹ Agroscope (AGS), Research Group Agricultural Landscapes and Biodiversity, 8049 Zurich, Switzerland

² Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement (INRAE), UMR SAS, 35000 Rennes, France

³ Thünen Institute of Climate-Smart Agriculture (Thünen), 38116 Braunschweig, Germany

9.1. Introduction

Agroforestry systems are “land use systems in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land” (European Parliament - Council of the European Union, 2013) or as defined by FAO (FAO, 2015b) “land-use systems and technologies where woody perennials (trees, shrubs, palms, bamboos, etc.) are deliberately used on the same land management units as agricultural crops and/or animals, in some form of spatial arrangement or temporal sequence”.

In Europe, these production systems have a long history as they i.) served as a primary source of food, fodder and resources and / or ii.) protected against weather extremes (e.g., wind, sun) and site disadvantages (e.g., slopes). In parts of Europe, they are still widespread and especially in southern Europe very prominent, e.g., the Dehesa and Montado systems (holm oak and cork oak with grazing pigs) still cover about 6.8 million hectares in Spain and Portugal.

Hence, due to the huge diversity of biogeographical regions in Europe, the variations of agroforestry systems adapted to local conditions (soil, climate, culture) are huge, too. Therefore, agroforestry systems in agricultural land are mostly divided into silvopastoral systems (woody elements with forage and animal production) and silvoarable systems (woody elements intercropped with annual or perennial crops). But there are numerous more types and combinations for example hedgerows, windbreaks, riparian buffer strips as lines of woody elements bordering farmland or forest farming in forest land.

All these systems are known to store significant quantities of C in above- and below-ground biomass. They are appreciated for their positive impact on climate mitigation and proposed as a C farming scheme in Europe (European Commission et al., 2021). Studies exist on aboveground biomass growth in various European agroforestry systems, e.g., olive trees in Italy (Spinelli and Picchi, 2010), poplar tree development in England (Burgess et al., 2005; Graves et al., 2010) or short rotation coppice in Germany (Graß et al., 2020). However, quantifying the amount of C stored in soils remains challenging. Limited information exists for determining a C sequestration potential. This is due to the broad range of agroforestry systems as well as the variation on tree species and age, as well as soil type and biogeographical region.

Two recently published papers prove a good overview of this topic. The first study by Drexler et al. (2021) focussed on the C storage potential of hedges. While they found good data on above-ground C stocks, the below-ground C stocks especially below-ground biomass was only

mentioned in one source. They found that above-ground biomass stock was $47 \pm 29 \text{ t C ha}^{-1}$ on average and below-ground biomass stock (roots) was in a similar range of $44 \pm 28 \text{ t C ha}^{-1}$. In total, new established hedges on cropland could store between 2.1 and 5.2 $\text{t C ha}^{-1} \text{ year}^{-1}$ for a period of 50 and 20 years in and under the hedge (both biomass and SOC), respectively. The second source by Mayer et al. (2022) presents a metadata analysis on SOC including 61 observations in temperate regions including USA and Canada (alley-cropping $n=25$; hedges $n=26$; silvopastoral $n=10$). They found C sequestrations rates of hedges in topsoils of $0.32 \pm 0.26 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (0-20 cm) and in subsoils of $0.28 \pm 0.15 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (20-40 cm). Alley cropping ranked slightly lower with $0.26 \pm 1.15 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (0-20 cm) and $0.23 \pm 0.25 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (20-40 cm) and silvopastoral systems even showed slight losses (0.17 ± 0.50 and $0.03 \pm 0.26 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).

Moreover, while the systems have a long tradition and were / are widespread in Europe, scientific literature is rare. LTEs, which are common in agricultural and / or forest research, seldomly cover agroforestry. Therefore, there is less data on long-term effects of trees and bushes within agricultural fields. One of the longest agroforestry field trials exists in Restinclières in southern France and was started in 1995. There, too, the rotation period for harvesting the trees has not yet ended. Consequently, the existing literature is limited to individual time periods (single measurements) and does not provide an overall picture of the lifetime of an agroforestry system. Moreover, literature on hedgerow systems also mostly lack the year of installation and therefore also fails to provide profound lifetime data to model overall performance of the systems.

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of agroforestry systems on SOC stocks by using data from European field observations (e.g., impact of an existing tree line on SOC compared with SOC in a place of the field that does not experience the impact of the tree line) and derive EFs.

9.2. Methodology

The data collection focussed on agroforestry systems in Europe. That resulted in a data set with a bundle of different systems. Some of them only covered by one or two studies.

The data extraction of the CarboSeq crop and soil management database (version 2023_03_13, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8130174, <https://zenodo.org/record/8130174>) followed the query:

Land use 'Agro-forestry areas' vs 'other' related

Cropping system 'Hedgerows / shelter belt' vs 'other'

Cropping system 'Silvopasture' vs 'other'

Cropping system 'Alley-cropping' vs 'other'

Crops 'Trees' vs 'other'.

In total, we compiled data from 36 agroforestry studies in Europe (200 pairs). They focussed on traditional (permanent) agroforestry such as Dehesa and Montado (5 studies- 24 pairs), on fruit plantations including olive orchards (11 studies – 34 pairs), on high-stem trees in arable land, i.e. so-called alley-cropping systems (4 studies – 70pairs), on hedges as field border (6 studies, 70 pairs), on short-rotation copies (4 studies – 75 pairs), on vineyards (3 studies – 8 pairs), and on silvopasture high-stem trees in pasture (3 studies -10 pairs). Most of the data could not be used because of the experimental set up or because the experiments were located outside of Europe.

In this report we focus on agricultural land only and selected two types of modern agroforestry systems:

- Agroforestry with Hedges (Hedgerows planting) - Additional planting of lines of shrubs or small trees, often forming a boundary or fence

Reference: cropland or grassland without hedges

- Alley-cropping agroforestry with single trees (tree planting) - Planting of single trees in lines within the field (covering between 10-20% of the field).

Reference: cropland without trees

For each of the sites, relative EFs were calculated based on the methodology presented in Chapter 3.

9.3. Results

The final dataset in the analysis includes 6 experiments located in 4 different countries and 3 different climatic zones with 17 pairs of treatments and control (i.e., 12 in Belgium, 3 in France, 1 in United Kingdom, 1 in Switzerland). 12 pairs focus on hedge systems, another 5 pairs on alley-cropping and all pairs are in or around cropland.

The spatial distribution of the selected LTEs for irrigation is shown in Figure 9-1.

Figure 9-1: Spatial distribution of selected long-term field experiments in Europe

The main climate and soil characteristics of each pair in each country are summarized in Table 9-1.

Table 9-1: Overview of agroforestry studies classified by climatic zone, aridity class and soil type

Country	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Sandy loam	Loam	Silt loam	Clay	NA
Belgium	Atlantic	Humid	3	9	-	-	-
France	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	-	1	0	-	1
France	Continental	Humid	-	-	1	-	-
Switzerland	Continental	Humid	1	-	-	-	-
United Kingdom	Atlantic	Humid	-	-	-	1	-

The summary of the range of the data in the dataset are presented in the Table 9-2.

Table 9-2: Summary for agroforestry systems of selected parameters in this analysis

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median
Sampling depth (cm)	23	40	26.24	23
Experiment duration (years)	7	19	15.5	18
SOC stock of the control (Mg ha ⁻¹)	9.00	37.89	15.98	12.60
SOC stock of the treatment (Mg ha ⁻¹)	9.80	51.60	20.94	16.40
Clay content (%)	11.39	55.00	18.80	15.16

Annual precipitation (mm)	646	1270	784	778
Annual mean temperature (°C)	9.2	14.3	10.5	10.1
Average aridity index	0.47	1.42	0.90	0.90
Relative EF	0.91	1.81	1.26	1.23

Figure 9-2: Distribution of selected parameters in the analysis

As the amount of input data was low and focused on cropland, we bundled the two study systems and explored them together. The observed relative EF for all systems (below hedgerow and in the trees strip of alley-cropping) ranged **between 0.91 and 1.81** for the tree or hedge area with the average value among all observations to be **1.26** (SD ± 0.21 , SE ± 0.05).

Only small differences occurred between hedge systems and alley-cropping systems, with an average EF value of 1.29 (SD ± 0.23 , SE ± 0.06) for hedgerow systems and an average EF value of 1.19 (SD ± 0.09 , SE ± 0.01) for alley-cropping systems. These differences are not significant, nor are they reliable due to the small number of input data.

Figure 9-3: Relative Emission Factor of alley cropping (n=5 pairs) and hedge systems (n=12 pairs)

Different variables were considered to explore the dataset. These included climate variables (climatic zone, aridity class, annual precipitation, mean annual temperature), soil-related variables (clay content, USDA soil type) and variables related to the system (system age, tree species). None of the mentioned variable showed significant effects in relation to the relative EFs tested by ANOVA from LM (Table 9-3). The sample size is too small, very unbalanced (4 alley cropping, 13 hedges // 13 Atlantic, 2 Mediterranean, 2 Continental), and therefore not reliable.

Table 9-3: Results of ANOVA tests on the effect of selected parameters on emission factors

	F-value	p-value
System (alley cropping – hedge)	0.783	0.390
Tree Species	0.241	0.866
Climatic zone	0.348	0.712
Aridity class	0.52	0.482
Soil type	0.317	0.813
Clay Content	0.017	0.897
Annual Mean Temperature	0.36	0.557
Annual Precipitation	0	0.999

9.4. Discussion

Agroforestry systems are championed to store C and therefore be an active C sink in Europe. While this is supported by a large body of research for the above-ground C stock, the below-ground soil C stock is hardly studied. This is due to: i.) the number of agroforestry experiments, especially LTEs, being very small; ii.) the existing systems are still very young; and iii.) the current studies hardly cover the entire life cycle of a system (tree life).

The existing literature (e.g., Drexler et al., 2021; Mayer et al., 2022) gives us a hint that agroforestry systems have indeed a C storage potential. But due to the huge variety of these systems (trees species and age, hedges, etc.) as well as soil type and biogeographical region and in line with the reduced number of literatures, we lack to provide robust data. Further research is needed to provide this essential information for both land managers as well as policy makers as baseline for resilient C (storage) policies.

9.5. Conclusion – Proposed emission factors

We suggest using the same EF value for both – hedgerow and alley cropping systems – of **1.26** (SD: ± 0.21 , SE: ± 0.05). The value represents exclusively the area covered with woody elements, i.e., either the area of the tree strip in alley-cropping systems or the area covered by hedges.

10. General outlook

To accurately measure C sequestration in the soils, direct measurements of SOC content through soil sampling and laboratory analyses are necessary. These measurements provide an estimation of changes in SOC stocks over time and allow for the calculation of potential C sequestration rates. However, EFs are also commonly used to estimate greenhouse gas emissions, including CO₂ emissions / C sequestration potential resulting from specific activities, such as changes in land use or land management practices that affect SOC stocks.

The use of EFs to estimate the effects of agricultural management practices on SOC stocks is an important step towards understanding the capacity of these practices to contribute to climate change mitigation or even C sequestration in soils and has several advantages. First, EFs provide a standardized approach for estimating C sequestration potential across different practices and regions. This allows for the comparison of different practices and facilitates the development of policies and incentives to promote climate-friendly practices which are potentially more effective at sequestering C. Additionally, using EFs can be more cost-effective than direct measurement of SOC, which is time-consuming and expensive especially on a large spatial scale. Finally, using LTEs as a data source can increase the robustness of the results as they provide more accurate measurements of SOC changes over time.

However, as with any method, there are potential limitations to the validity and robustness of the results. While EFs can be useful for estimating SOC stock differences between two management practices, they do not provide information on whether the set of practices that a farmer applies (fertilisation, tillage, cover crops, crops in the rotation) lead to C sequestration or C loss mitigation. C sequestration and SOC loss mitigation are two related but distinct concepts that are both captured by EFs. C sequestration refers to the process of increasing net SOC stocks globally over time, while SOC loss mitigation refers to the reduction in SOC losses due to the changes in management practices. The EFs as calculated in this document consider only the latest timepoint to estimate the difference between the practices at that point and do not consider the initial conditions. This limitation is captured in Figure 10-1 in which the potential C sequestration induced by a measure is shown with the orange arrow, while the EFs estimate the difference between the “Business as usual” line and the “with implementation of a measure line”. In the cases a and b, the EFs indeed estimate the C sequestration potential caused by the implementation of the specific measure, but in the cases c and d this is not the case. This can lead to an overestimation or underestimation of the actual C sequestration of a given practice.

Also, by not considering the initial SOC stock when interpreting the magnitude of the SOC stock change (absolute SOC stock change), the results can be misleading. For example, if two fields one with a low initial SOC stock level and a second one with higher SOC stocks are subjected to the same management practice that leads to a specific EF, the resulting absolute SOC stock change will be higher in the field with high initial SOC stocks than with the lower. On the other

hand, if a field with a low initial SOC stock level is subjected to a management practice that leads to a moderate increase in SOC stocks, the resulting EF may be relatively high. On the other hand, if a field with a high initial SOC stock level is subjected to the same practice that leads to the same actual SOC stocks increase, the resulting EF may be relatively low. This can create confusion when interpreting EFs, as a higher EF may be mistakenly interpreted as indicating a higher rate of C sequestration in soils.

Figure 10-1: Scenarios of temporal dynamic of SOC stock changes between a business-as-usual practice and a practice to enhance SOC. (source:(Don et al., 2023))

Another limitation is that EFs are typically based on data from a limited number of sites, which may not represent the full range of environmental and management conditions across different regions. This can result in uncertainty in the estimates, particularly when extrapolating EFs to regions with different conditions. Additionally, EFs may not fully capture the complexity of the C cycle and the interactions between different management practices, which can result in underestimation or overestimation of the effects of certain practices.

To overcome these limitations, it is important to complement the use of EFs with additional information on the initial SOC stock levels and the temporal dynamics of SOC changes. For instance, LTEs that monitor changes in SOC stocks over multiple years can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of different management practices for C sequestration in soils or C loss mitigation. Furthermore, additional data on soil properties, climate conditions, and land use history can help to identify factors that influence the effectiveness of management practices for SOC management.

Overall, estimating EFs to quantify SOC stocks due to changes in agricultural management practices is a valuable tool but it is important to be aware of the limitations and potential sources of uncertainty in the results. Future research can help to improve the accuracy and robustness of these estimates by complementing the use of EFs with additional information, incorporating more detailed information on initial SOC content and management practices, as well as by using advanced modelling techniques to better account for environmental variability and data availability limitations.

11. General conclusions

In this study, we have conducted an extensive analysis using data collected from various LTEs that employed both control and treatment crop management practices. The primary objective was to calculate EFs to estimate the effect on SOC stocks, specifically within the European context.

The key novelty of this research lies in its focused approach, specifically addressing the EFs and SOC stocks at a European scale, in contrast to the broader scope adopted by the current IPCC recommendations. By narrowing our investigation to the European scale, we have been able to provide more regionally specific EFs, offering valuable insights into the C dynamics of European agricultural systems. Furthermore, this study has made a significant contribution by introducing EFs for management practices that were previously not included in the IPCC suggestions.

In Table 11-1, an overview of the proposed EFs as determined through analysis is presented. In most cases, different variables were found to have a significant impact on the EFs. However, the availability and distribution of data did not justify the use of different EFs for various categories or ranges of these variables.

For instance, in the cases of cover crops, crop diversification, and crop residues, the climatic zone was initially identified as a statistically significant predictor variable. Nevertheless, it was observed that the distribution of available data was unbalanced among and within different climatic zones. This imbalance can lead to poor model performance and hinder the interpretation of results, making it unjustifiable to use different EFs for each climatic zone. Therefore, it is recommended to utilize the average value of EFs in Europe from the entire dataset in the majority of cases.

Table 11-1 also presents the number of treatment pairs, average duration of the experiments, sampling depth, and ranges of important variables considered in the analyses. When using the EFs, it is essential to take into account also the range of important pedoclimatic variables in the dataset used to estimate the EFs. It is crucial to critically evaluate these values when interpreting the results and making suggestions for which or where a management option is preferred / suitable to be applied. The use of EFs outside of these ranges should be approached with caution.

The findings of this study have implications for policymakers, researchers, and land managers, as they provide a more accurate and localized understanding of the potential effects of specific management practices on SOC stocks in European agricultural systems. This knowledge can inform decision-making processes aimed at sustainable land management and climate change mitigation strategies tailored to the unique conditions of the European region.

Table 11-1: : Overview of the proposed European EFs or regression equations for each management practice. Information about the data as well as ranges of important variables which were included in the analysis datasets are shown.

Management option	Proposed emission factor	Mean emission factor (±std)	Treatment pairs considered	Average sampling depth (cm)	Average experiment duration (years)	SOC stock of the control (Mg ha ⁻¹)	Clay content (%)	Annual precipitation (mm)
Cover crops vs No cover crops	1.06	1.06 (±0.08)	27	24.2	11.3	31.5-68.8	9-45	386-929
Increased share of forage legumes	EF = 1.182198 + 0.003957 * percentage difference (%) - 0.129105 * SOC of the control per cm (Mg ha-1 cm-1)	1.08(±0.21)	39	23.2	28.1	11.4-88.5	3-24	428-880
Straw left on field and incorporated vs removal	EF = 1.114560 - 0.075746 * SOC of the control per cm (Mg ha-1 cm-1) + 0.214673 * crop rotation (decimal) + 0.002988 * Clay content (%) - 0.000147 * annual rainfall (mm)	1.09 (±0.12)	38	23.5	29.5	14.7-97.7	8-43	520-1345
Zero-tillage vs inversion tillage	1.14	1.14 (±0.25)	27	28.4	14.3	13.3-99.06	5-78	332-1164
Non-inversion vs inversion tillage	1.05	1.05 (± 0.18)	46	22.8	15.2	4.1-97.7	2.5-64	332-1413
Irrigated vs non irrigated systems	NA	NA	20					

Agroforestry with Hedges & alley-cropping vs cropland without trees	1.26	1.26 (±0.21)	17	26.2	15.5	9-37	11-55	646-1270
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Appendix I

Data to support the analysis of Chapter 4: Cover crops

Table A1: Experiment information and variables used in the analysis similar for all treatments within the experiment (Climate and soil variables)

Database version: 03.10.2022				Cover crops				
Experiment ID	Country	Latitude (decimal degrees)	Longitude (decimal degrees)	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Average aridity index	Clay (%)	Soil type (USDA)
CROPSYS_Flakkebjerg	Denmark	55.317	11.383	Continental	Humid	0.77	14.3	Sandy loam (SL)
CoverCrop_Arajuez10years	Spain	40.065	-3.541	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.25	25.0	Loam (L)
CROPSYS_Foulum	Denmark	56.300	9.340	Continental	Humid	1.07	9.0	Sandy loam (SL)
Askov straw disposal experiment	Denmark	55.280	9.060	Atlantic	Humid	1.26	11.8	Sandy loam (SL)
mulch_Ruprechtshofen	Austria	48.130	15.217	Continental	Humid	0.74		
Meleti	Italy	45.124	9.832	Continental	Humid	0.79	12.0	Sandy loam (SL)
GLBR	France	43.520	1.500	Atlantic	Dry sub-humid	0.58	25.6	Loam (L)
puch_iosdv	Germany	48.190	11.213	Continental	Humid	1.08	20.0	Silt loam (SiL)
CENTS Foulum	Denmark	56.500	9.350	Continental	Humid	1.07	9.2	Sandy loam (SL)
Conventional and organic farming	Estonia	58.365	26.666	Boreal	Humid	0.86	9.5	Sandy loam (SL)
80_Arvalis-Institut du Vegetal	France	48.327	8.382	Atlantic	Humid	0.66	24.6	Silt loam (SiL)
SAPKO12V32.1	Italy	43.667	10.317	Mediterranean	Humid	0.66	15.5	Loam (L)
89_Lanna	Sweden	58.210	13.080	Boreal	Humid	0.82	45.0	Silty clay loam (SiCL)

Table A2: Information about each pair and variables used in the analysis different for each pair (e.g., SOC of the control, EF, management variables)

Database version: 03.10.2022		Cover crops	

Experiment ID	treatid_C	treatid_T	Treatment definition_C	Treatment definition_T	Soil depth (cm)	Duration of treatment (years)	SOC_C (Mg ha ⁻¹)	EF	cover crop diversity	amendments	tillage system
CROPSYS_Flakk ebjerg	OG+M-C	OG+M+C	Organic cropping system including grass-clover and manure without cover crops	Organic cropping system including grass-clover and manure with cover crops	25	12	30.75	1.21	mixture	Organic amendment	inversion tillage
CROPSYS_Flakk ebjerg	OB+M-C	OB+M+C	Organic cropping system including beans and manure without cover crops	Organic cropping system including beans and manure with cover crops	25	12	35.32	0.90	mixture	Organic amendment	inversion tillage
CROPSYS_Flakk ebjerg	CB+F-C	CB+F+C	Organic cropping system including beans and mineral fertilizer without cover crops	Organic cropping system including beans and mineral fertilizer with cover crops	25	12	29.52	1.27	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	inversion tillage
CoverCrop_Arajez10years	Fa	Ba	No cover crop between summer main crop harvest (October) and next summer main crop (April)	Barley cover crop between summer main crop harvest (October) and next summer main crop (April)	20	10	31.51	1.10	single	Inorganic fertilizer	non-inversion tillage
CoverCrop_Arajez10years	Fa	Ve	No cover crop between summer main crop harvest (October) and next summer main crop (April)	Vetch cover crop between summer main crop harvest (October) and next summer main crop (April)	20	10	31.51	1.09	single	Inorganic fertilizer	non-inversion tillage
CROPSYS_Foulum	OGM+M-CC	OGM+M+CC	Organic cropping system including grass-clover and manure without cover crops	Organic cropping system including grass-clover and manure with cover crops	25	22	66.15	1.19	mixture	Organic amendment	non-inversion tillage

CROPSYS_Foulum	OGL+M-CC	OGL+M+CC	Organic cropping system including beans and manure without cover crops	Organic cropping system including beans and manure with cover crops	25	22	68.78	1.01	mixture	Organic amendment	non-inversion tillage
Askov straw disposal experiment	WithoutCC	WithCC	Removal of straw	With an undersown ryegrass cover crop	20	38	44.46	1.05	single	Inorganic fertilizer	inversion tillage
mulch_Ruprechtshofen	no mulch_no rotation	mulch_no rotation	no mulch and no rotation	mulch and no rotation	20	5	24.26	1.10	single	Inorganic fertilizer	non-inversion tillage
Meleti	T1 (noCC)	T2 (rye CC)	reference, mineral fertilizer	mineral fertilizer + green manure (rye)	30	6	39.40	1.02	single	Both	Inversion tillage
Meleti	T1 (noCC)	T3 (hairy vetch CC)	reference, mineral fertilizer	mineral fertilizer + green manure (hairy vetch)	30	6	39.40	0.98	single	Both	Inversion tillage
GLBR	GL0-BF	GL0-CC	no grain legume in the rotation, bare fallow	no grain legume in the rotation, cover crop	30	6	37.31	1.05	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	Inversion tillage
GLBR	GL1-BF	GL1-CC	1 grain legume in the rotation, bare fallow	1 grain legume in the rotation, cover crop	30	6	34.38	1.08	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	Inversion tillage
GLBR	GL2-BF	GL2-CC	2 grain legumes in the rotation, bare fallow	2 grain legumes in the rotation, cover crop	30	6	33.65	1.14	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	Inversion tillage
puch_iosdv	Stroh	Stroh + Zwischenfrucht	No organic amendments	Straw + cover crop (leguminous)	10	11	14.47	1.02	single	No	
puch_iosdv	Gülle, 60 m3/ha + stroh	Gülle, 60 m3/ha + stroh+ zwischenfrucht	Slurry at 60 m3/h + Straw	Slurry at 60 m3/h + Straw + Cover crop (rapeseed)	10	11	15.71	0.99	single	Organic amendment	
CENTS Foulum	R4	R5	diverse rotation, straw retained	diverse rotation and fodder radish, straw retained	25	7	7.32	1.03	single	Both	non-inversion tillage
Conventional and organic farming	O-control	O-CC	control treatment for organic farming systems	control treatment for organic farming	25	10	52.70	1.02	single	No	inversion tillage

				systems with cover crops								
80_Arvalis-Institut du Vegetal	FIT_CM1 (control to CM2)	FIT_CM2 (CC treatment)	Combination of full inversion tillage and crop management 1	Combination of full inversion tillage and crop management 2	31.4	8	45.97	1.00	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	inversion tillage	
80_Arvalis-Institut du Vegetal	ST_CM1 (control to CM2)	ST_CM2 (CC treatment)	Combination of shallow tillage and crop management 1	Combination of shallow tillage and crop management 2	31.4	8	44.58	1.07	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	non-inversion tillage	
80_Arvalis-Institut du Vegetal	NT_CM1 (control to CM2)	NT_CM2 (CC treatment)	Combination of no tillage and crop management 1	Combination of no tillage and crop management 2	31.4	8	44.50	1.09	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	Zero tillage	
80_Arvalis-Institut du Vegetal	FIT_CM6 (control to CM5)	FIT_CM5 (CC treatment)	Combination of full inversion tillage and crop management 6	Combination of full inversion tillage and crop management 5	31.4	8	44.86	1.00	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	inversion tillage	
80_Arvalis-Institut du Vegetal	ST_CM6 (control to CM5)	ST_CM5 (CC treatment)	Combination of shallow tillage and crop management 6	Combination of shallow tillage and crop management 5	31.4	8	44.78	1.00	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	non-inversion tillage	
80_Arvalis-Institut du Vegetal	NT_CM6 (control to CM5)	NT_CM5 (CC treatment)	Combination of no tillage and crop management 6	Combination of no tillage and crop management 5	31.4	8	44.95	1.02	mixture	Inorganic fertilizer	Zero tillage	
SAPKO12V32.1	control	BJ cover crop (B. juncea)	conventional tillage: cover crop ploughing down to 30 cm	cover crop: Brassica juncea	10	15	36.57	1.01	single	Inorganic fertilizer		
SAPKO12V32.1	control	VV cover crop (V. villosa)	conventional tillage: cover crop ploughing down to 30 cm	cover crop: Vicia villosa	10	15	36.57	1.13	single	Inorganic fertilizer		
89_Lanna	No CC	CC	no cover crop	cover crop	20	16	7.39	1.10	single	No	inversion tillage	

Data to support the analysis of Chapter 5: Crops and crop diversification

Table A3: Experiment information and variables used in the analysis similar for all treatments within the experiment (Climate and soil variables)

Database version: 16.11.2022		Increased share of legumes in the rotation								
Experiment ID	Country	Latitude (decimal degrees)	Longitude (decimal degrees)	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Average aridity index	Annual mean temperature (°C)	Annual precipitation (mm)	Clay (%)	Soil type (USDA)
Apelsvoll	Norway	60.420	10.510	Boreal	Humid	1.03	4.5	683	18.0	Loam (L)
CHRIS90V94.1	Denmark	55.467	9.117	Atlantic	Humid	1.23	7.9	880	12.5	Sandy loam (SL)
Crop rotation experiment (CR)	Italy	45.350	11.967	Continental	Humid	0.74	13.2	783	15.0	Loam (L)
CROPSYS_Flakkebjerg	Denmark	55.317	11.383	Continental	Humid	0.77	8.6	601	14.3	Sandy loam (SL)
CROPSYS_Foulum	Denmark	56.300	9.340	Continental	Humid	1.07	7.6	775	9.0	Sandy loam (SL)
El Encin	Spain	40.483	-3.367	Mediterranean	Semi- Arid	0.29	14.1	434	21.0	Loamy sand (LS)
Experminetal farm near As Rotation & Fertilization	Norway	59.650	10.783	Boreal	Humid	1.06	5.8	788		Clay loam (CL)
Ihinger Hof	Germany	48.745	8.924	Continental	Humid	0.91	8.6	797	21.0	Silt loam (SIL)
INIA-LTE-ROT	Spain	40.530	-3.330	Mediterranean	Semi- Arid	0.28	13.9	428	12.9	Sandy loam (SL)
Kaltinenai	Lithuania	55.567	22.483	Boreal	Humid	1.08	6.0	771		Sandy loam (SL)
KUNZO13V59.1	Czech Republic	50.087	14.291	Continental	Dry sub- humid	0.58	8.1	498		Clay loam (CL)
La	Sweden	58.000	13.000	Boreal	Humid	1.15	6.2	803		Sandy loam (SL)
Lo	Sweden	55.669	13.109	Continental	Humid	0.76	8.3	587		Sandy loam (SL)
Lodi - POC	Italy	45.300	9.500	Continental	Humid	0.84	12.6	861	12.0	Sandy loam (SL)
MASCOT	Italy	43.667	10.317	Mediterranean	Humid	0.66	14.2	849	22.9	Loam (L)
Melle2	Belgium	50.983	3.817	Atlantic	Humid	0.93	10.5	786	8.6	Sandy loam (SL)
O_Ler	Denmark	55.467	9.117	Atlantic	Humid	1.23	7.9	880	9.8	Sandy loam (SL)
Ro	Sweden	63.808	20.234	Boreal	Humid	1.03	3.0	630		Silt loam (SIL)

rot_Etzdorf	Germany	51.430	11.760	Continental	Dry sub-humid	0.60	9.1	528	20.0	Silt loam (SiL)
Torrepadierne	Spain	42.220	-4.379	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.33	11.7	430		Clay loam (CL)
U_Sand	Denmark	55.467	9.117	Atlantic	Humid	1.23	7.9	880	3.1	Loamy sand (LS)
10_CREA experimental farm Manfredini	Italy	41.450	15.510	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.35	15.6	499	17.5	Silt loam (SiL)
3_CREA experimental farm Manfredini	Italy	41.450	15.500	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.35	15.6	499	50.0	Clay loam (CL)
CENTS Flakkebjerg	Denmark	55.317	11.383	Continental	Humid	0.77	8.6	599	14.7	Sandy loam (SL)
CENTS Foulum	Denmark	56.500	9.350	Continental	Humid	1.07	7.7	745	9.2	Sandy loam (SL)
GLBR	France	43.520	1.500	Atlantic	Dry sub-humid	0.58	13.1	695	25.6	Loam (L)
Harste	Germany	51.607	9.864	Continental	Humid	0.85	8.9	675	10.0	Silt loam (SiL)
Malagon	Spain	37.755	-4.536	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.30	17.7	534	69.4	Clay (C)
Pietranera	Italy	37.500	13.517	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.29	17.3	456	47.1	Clay (C)
RYCHC06V52.1	Poland	53.596	19.855	Continental	Humid	0.82	7.3	637		Silt loam (SiL)
Folha 4 S da EAV	Portugal	40.639	-7.911	Mediterranean	Humid	1.23	14.0	1668		Sandy loam (SL)
ZUAZO20	Spain	36.920	-3.490	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.25	15.4	417	20.0	Loam (L)

Table A4: Information about each pair and variables used in the analysis different for each pair (e.g., SOC of the control, EF, management variables)

Database version: 16.11.2022				Increased share of legumes in the rotation								
	Experiment ID	treatid_C	treatid_T	Treatment definition_C	Treatment definition_T	Soil depth (cm)	Duration of treatment (years)	SOC_C (Mg ha ⁻¹)	EF	% difference	scope	establishment
Used in the final	Apelsvoll	CS5	CS6	Organic mixed dairy: wheat/barley/ley/ley//slurry use,	Organic mixed dairy: barley/ley/ley/ley//slurry use, ploughing in spring	30	15	88.49	0.97	25	plant	multianual

				ploughing in spring								
CHRIS90V94.1	2.0	1.0		Winter wheat-root crop-spring barley-flax	Winter wheat-root crop-spring barley-clover/grass ley	20	29	38.21	1.03	25	plant	annual
Crop rotation experiment (CR)	LI 4-year M	LI 6-year M		sugar beet-maize-wheat-maize, low input, mineral fertilization 70 N; 70 P; 90 K kg/ha/y	maize-sugar beet-maize-wheat-alfalfa (Medicago sativa L.)-alfalfa, low input, mineral fertilization 70 N; 70 P; 90 K kg/ha/y	20	38	19.05	1.28	33	plant	multianual
Crop rotation experiment (CR)	LI 4-year O	LI 6-year O		Sugar beet-maize-wheat-maize, low input, no fertilization	maize-sugar beet-maize-wheat-alfalfa (Medicago sativa L.)-alfalfa, low input, no fertilization	20	38	21.09	1.12	33	plant	multianual
Crop rotation experiment (CR)	HI 4-year O	HI 6-year O		Sugar beet-maize-wheat-maize, high input, no fertilization	maize-sugar beet-maize-wheat-alfalfa (Medicago sativa L.)-alfalfa, high input, no fertilization	20	38	21.47	1.06	33	plant	multianual
Crop rotation experiment (CR)	LI 4-year MM	LI 6-year MM		Sugar beet-maize-wheat-maize, low input, mineral fertilization 100 N; 50 P; 140 K kg/ha/y	maize-sugar beet-maize-wheat-alfalfa (Medicago sativa L.)-alfalfa, low input, mineral fertilization 100 N; 50 P; 140 K kg/ha/y	20	38	22.34	1.03	33	plant	multianual
Crop rotation experiment (CR)	HI 4-year MM	HI 6-year MM		Sugar beet-maize-wheat-maize, high input, mineral fertilization 100 N;	maize-sugar beet-maize-wheat-alfalfa (Medicago sativa L.)-alfalfa, high input, mineral fertilization	20	38	20.69	1.00	33	plant	multianual

			50 P; 140 K kg/ha/y	100 N; 50 P; 140 K kg/ha/y								
Crop rotation experiment (CR)	HI 4-year M	HI 6-year M	sugar beet–maize–wheat–maize, high input, mineral fertilization 70 N; 70 P; 90 K kg/ha/y	maize–sugar beet–maize–wheat–alfalfa (Medicago sativa L.)–alfalfa, high input, mineral fertilization 70 N; 70 P; 90 K kg/ha/y	20	38	23.27	0.99	33	plant	multianual	
CROPSYS_Flak kebberg	OB+M-C	OG+M-C	Organic cropping system including beans and manure without cover crops	Organic cropping system including grass-clover and manure without cover crops	25	11	35.88	0.91	25	plant	multianual	
CROPSYS_Fou lum	OGL+M-CC	OGM+M-CC	Organic cropping system including beans and manure without cover crops	Organic cropping system including grass-clover and manure without cover crops	25	22	68.43	0.97	25	plant	multianual	
El Encin	CM_CT	WV_CT	Cereal monoculture + conventional tillage	Wheat-vetch rotation + conventional tillage	30	11	29.50	1.13	50	plant	annual	
El Encin	CM_ZT	WV_ZT	Cereal monoculture + no tillage	Wheat-vetch rotation + no tillage	30	11	34.90	1.05	50	plant	annual	
El Encin	CM_MT	WV_MT	Cereal monoculture + minimum tillage	Wheat-vetch rotation + minimum tillage	30	11	32.10	1.00	50	plant	annual	
Experimetal farm near As Rotation & Fertilization	I	IV	Continuous cereal cropping (6yrs)	Cereal crops (2 yrs)+ley (4yrs)	20	48	73.13	1.21	67	plant	multianual	
Experimetal farm near As	I	III	Continuous cereal cropping (6yrs)	Cereal crops (4 yrs)+ley (2yrs)	20	48	73.13	1.14	33	plant	multianual	

	Rotation & Fertilization												
	lhinger Hof	lh_plough-rape	lh_plough-leg	ploughed (25 cm), rape-cereal rotation	ploughed (25 cm), legume-cereal rotation (more diverse)	25	14	39.24	0.91	37.5	plan t	multian nual	
	lhinger Hof	lh_rot-rape	lh_rot-leg	rotary cultivation (10-12 cm), rape-cereal rotation	rotary cultivation (10-12 cm), legume-cereal rotation (more diverse)	25	14	44.08	0.90	37.5	plan t	multian nual	
	INIA-LTE-ROT	MT-Monocrop	MT-Rot	wheat monocrop in Minimum tillage	4-year rotation in Minimum tillage	30	18	25.92	0.97	25	plan t	annual	
	INIA-LTE-ROT	NT-Monocrop	NT-Rot	wheat monocrop in No tillage	4-year rotation in No tillage	30	18	32.99	0.88	25	plan t	annual	
	INIA-LTE-ROT	CT-Monocrop	CT-Rot	wheat monocrop in Conventional tillage	4-year rotation in Conventional tillage	30	18	29.28	0.84	25	plan t	annual	
	Kaltinenai	grain-grass crop rotation	grass-grain I crop rotation	1) winter rye, 2-4) spring barley, 5-6) CT	1) winter rye, 2) spring barley, 3-6) CT.	20	18	73.74	1.10	34	plan t	multian nual	
	KUNZO13V59. 1	Field B +Csl+ST	Field IV +Csl+ST	alternate growing of sugar beet and spring wheat +Slurry+straw	9-year crop rotation involving winter wheat, sugar beet, spring barley undersown by lucerne, lucerne, winter wheat, sugar beet, spring barley, and potatoes +Slurry+straw	20	55	39.29	1.06	33	plan t	multian nual	
	KUNZO13V59. 1	Field B +FYM+NPK	Field IV +FYM+NPK	alternate growing of sugar beet and spring wheat	9-year crop rotation involving winter wheat, sugar beet,	20	55	44.11	1.03	33	plan t	multian nual	

				+NPK fertilization+FYM	spring undersown by lucerne, lucerne, wheat, sugar beet, spring barley, and potatoes +NPK fertilization+FYM								
KUNZO13V59.1	Field B+NPK	Field +NPK	IV	alternate growing of sugar beet and spring wheat+NPK fertilization	9-year crop rotation involving winter wheat, sugar beet, spring barley undersown by lucerne, lucerne, winter wheat, sugar beet, spring barley, and potatoes, +NPK fertilization	20	55	39.99	1.01	33	plant	multianual	
KUNZO13V59.1	Field B +Csl+ST+NPK	Field +Csl+ST+NPK	IV	alternate growing of sugar beet and spring wheat+NPK fertilization +Slury+straw	9-year crop rotation involving winter wheat, sugar beet, spring barley undersown by lucerne, lucerne, winter wheat, sugar beet, spring barley, and potatoes +Slury+straw +NPK fertilization	20	55	43.66	0.96	33	plant	multianual	
KUNZO13V59.1	Field B +FYM	Field +FYM	IV	alternate growing of sugar beet and spring wheat +FYM fertilization	9-year crop rotation involving winter wheat, sugar beet, spring barley	20	55	47.00	0.88	33	plant	multianual	

				undersown by lucerne, lucerne, winter wheat, sugar beet, spring barley, and potatoes +FYM								
La	R3-0020 cereals	R3-0021 ley	cereals	ley	20	16	48.96	1.24	75	plan t	multian nual	
Lo	R3-0020 cereals	R3-0021 ley	cereals	ley	20	16	38.07	1.27	75	plan t	multian nual	
Lodi - POC	Lodi - POC2 R1-SLM	Lodi - POC2 R6-SLM	one annually-repeated double crop +Cattle slurry application,	six-year rotation +Cattle slurry application,	30	11	48.10	0.97	50	plan t	multian nual	
Lodi - POC	Lodi - POC2 R1-FYM	Lodi - POC2 R6-FYM	one annually-repeated double crop +Farmyard manure application,	six-year rotation +Farmyard manure application,	30	11	61.06	0.88	50	plan t	multian nual	
MASCOT	t1	t2	conventional	organic	25	5	29.41	1.19	40	plan t	annual	
Melle2	PA	TG	permanent arable cropping since 1966 with forage crops	temporary ley-arable crop rotation, started in 1966 with 3 years of grass ley followed by 3 years of arable land cropped with forage crops	10	38	16.38	1.58	50	plan t	multian nual	
Melle2	PA	TA	permanent arable cropping since 1966 with forage crops	temporary arable crop-ley rotation, started in 1966 with 3 years of arable cropping followed by 3 years of grass ley	10	38	16.38	1.53	50	plan t	multian nual	

	O_Ler	6.0	7.0	Root crops	3 yr clover grass + 1 yr root crop	20	30	60.67	1.11	75	plant	multianual
	Ro	R3-0020 cereals	R3-0021 ley	cereals	ley	20	17	62.41	0.74	75	plant	multianual
	rot_Etzdorf	T4	T7	50% sugar beet rotation, 2/0 years cropping interval	20% sugar beet rotation, 4 years cropping interval	30	36	80.40	1.04	40	plant	multianual
	rot_Etzdorf	T4	T5	50% sugar beet rotation, 2/0 years cropping interval	25% sugar beet rotation, 3 years cropping interval	30	36	80.40	1.04	25	plant	annual
	Torrepadierne	R3	R5	CR-->1994-2001: cereal-cereal/2001-2004: legume-cereal-cereal-cereal	CR-->1994-2001: cereal-legume/2001-2004: legume-cereal-cereal-cereal	30	6	41.01	1.04	50	plant	annual
	U_Sand	6.0	7.0	Root crops	3 yr clover grass + 1 yr root crop	20	30	11.43	1.89	75	plant	multianual
Excluded because refer to pulses	10_CREA experimental farm Manfredini	Monocropping+ inversion till	Rotation+in version till	Durum wheat+ conventional till	Tick bean- durum wheat+ conventional till	20	24	27.35	1.12	50	pulses	annual
	10_CREA experimental farm Manfredini	Monocropping+ no till	Rotation+no till	Durum wheat+ zero till	Tick bean- durum wheat + zero till	25	24	64.81	1.08	50	pulses	annual
	3_CREA experimental farm Manfredini	t1	t3	Fertilized control-wheat monoculture	Rotation wheat-wheat-chickpea	20	16	26.46	1.05	33	pulses	annual
	CENTS Flakkebjerg	R1	R4	winter wheat rotation	diverse rotation, straw retained	30	7	66.14	1.04	14	pulses	annual

CENTS Flakkebjerg	R2	R4	winter cereals and rape seed	diverse rotation, straw retained	30	7	50.26	1.03	14	pulses	annual
CENTS Foulum	R2	R4	winter cereals and rape seed	diverse rotation, straw retained	30	7	22.04	1.02	14	pulses	annual
GLBR	GL0-BF	GL1-BF	no grain legume in the rotation, bare fallow	1 grain legume in the rotation, bare fallow	30	6	66.47	1.01	33	pulses	annual
GLBR	GL0-BF	GL2-BF	no grain legume in the rotation, bare fallow	2 grain legumes in the rotation, bare fallow	15	6	38.79	1.00	50	pulses	annual
Harste	rotation 1	rotation 3	sugar beet - winter wheat - winter wheat	sugar beet - winter wheat - rapeseed - winter wheat - pea	15	14	29.65	0.99	33	pulses	annual
Malagon	CT_wh+wh	CT_wh+ch	CT+2-year crop rotation of wheat-wheat	CT+2-year crop rotation of wheat-chickpea	30	20	18.47	0.98	50	pulses	annual
Malagon	CT_wh+wh	CT_wh+fb	CT+2-year crop rotation of wheat-wheat	CT+2-year crop rotation of wheat-faba bean	25	20	47.50	0.98	50	pulses	annual
Malagon	NT_wh+wh	NT_wh+ch	NT+2-year crop rotation of wheat-wheat	NT+2-year crop rotation of wheat-chickpea	30	20	59.10	0.97	50	pulses	annual
Malagon	NT_wh+wh	NT_wh+fb	NT+2-year crop rotation of wheat-wheat	NT+2-year crop rotation of wheat-faba bean	25	20	48.18	0.96	50	pulses	annual
Pietranera	WW-CT	WB-CT	ploughing + Continuous durum wheat rotation	ploughing + durum wheat/faba bean rotation	30	18	18.47	0.95	50	pulses	annual
Pietranera	WW-DL	WB-DL	dual layer tillage + Continuous durum wheat rotation	dual layer tillage + durum wheat/faba bean rotation	15	18	41.65	0.93	50	pulses	annual

	Pietranera	WW-NT	WB-NT	no tillage + Continuous durum wheat rotation	no tillage + durum wheat/faba bean rotation	30	18	74.88	0.93	50	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Flax	Faba bean	Flax monoculture	Faba monoculture bean	25	37	29.35	0.92	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Maize	Pea	Maize monoculture	Pea monoculture	15	37	35.30	0.92	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Oats	Faba bean	Oats monoculture	Faba monoculture bean	25	37	29.70	0.91	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Potato	Faba bean	Potato monoculture	Faba monoculture bean	30	37	74.88	0.91	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Rotation A	Faba bean	potato - oats - flax - winter rye - faba bean - winter triticale	Faba monoculture bean	25	37	29.98	0.90	83	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Rotation B	Pea	sugar beet - maize - spring barley - pea - winter rape - winter wheat	Pea monoculture	25	37	24.11	0.90	83	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Spring barley	Pea	Spring barley monoculture	Pea monoculture	15	37	32.45	0.89	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Sugar Beet	Pea	Sugar Beet monoculture	Pea monoculture	25	37	30.37	0.89	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Winter rape	Pea	Winter rape monoculture	Pea monoculture	20	37	25.30	0.89	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Winter Rye	Faba bean	Winter Rye monoculture	Faba monoculture bean	30	37	22.04	0.87	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Winter triticale	Faba bean	Winter triticale monoculture	Faba monoculture bean	25	37	31.82	0.85	100	puls es	annual
	RYCHC06V52. 1	Winter wheat	Pea	Winter wheat monoculture	Pea monoculture	25	37	31.99	0.85	100	puls es	annual

Data to support the analysis of Chapter 6: Crop residues

Table A5: Experiment information and variables used in the analysis similar for all treatments within the experiment (Climate and soil variables)

Database version: 24.10.2022									
Crop residues incorporation vs removal									
Experiment ID	Country	Latitude (decimal degrees)	Longitude (decimal degrees)	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Average aridity index	Annual mean temperature (°C)	Annual precipitation (mm)	Clay (%)
VE-5	Lithuania	55.72	21.45	Boreal	Humid	1.08	6.7	748	15.3
Rutzendorf_17	Austria	48.35	16.75	Continental	Dry sub-humid	0.60	9.1	540	23
Rottenhaus_17	Austria	48.20	15.25	Continental	Humid	0.72	8.5	836	16
Jable	Slovenia	46.13	14.57	Continental	Humid	1.53	9.5	1345	17
CENTS_Flakkebjerg	Denmark	55.32	11.38	Continental	Humid	0.77	8.4	713	15
CENTS_Foulum	Denmark	56.30	9.35	Continental	Humid	1.07	8	733	9
MATTSO_2a	Sweden	55.63	13.16	Continental	Humid	0.75	8.2	571	17.2
MATTSO_2b	Sweden	55.55	13.00	Continental	Humid	0.73	8.2	571	13.6
mulch_Ruprechtshofen	Austria	48.13	15.22	Continental	Humid	0.74	9	834	27.3
Revilheira Farm	Portugal	38.47	-7.47	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.35	15.6	572	31.1
67_Jokioinen	Finland						4.6	627	41.2
8_University of Bologna farm Cadriano	Italy	44.55	11.35	Continental	Dry sub-humid	0.58	13	700	28
HAZAR09V29.1	United Kingdom	50.77	-3.99	Atlantic	Humid	1.40	9	975	11
POWLS11V103.2a	United Kingdom	51.82	-0.35	Atlantic	Humid	0.87	10	700	23
POWLS11V103.2b	United Kingdom	52.03	-0.35	Atlantic	Humid	0.77	10	650	8
Osaker	Norway	59.38	11.03	Boreal	Humid	1.14	6	855	34
Longs Tours	Belgium	50.56	4.73	Atlantic	Humid	0.95	10	800	12
IteFertBS	Germany	52.30	10.45	Atlantic	Humid	0.74	8.8	618	12
MANOJ08V54.2	Serbia	45.19	19.50	Pannonian	Dry sub-humid	0.58	11.1	608	
Harste	Germany	51.61	9.86	Continental	Humid	0.85	9.5	624	10
Teagasc	Ireland	52.86	-6.91	Atlantic	Humid	1.20	9.4	824	17.33
Torrepadierne	Spain	42.22	-4.38	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.33	11	520	24.58
DOTN-3	Lithuania	55.38	23.87	Boreal	Humid	0.79	6.4	568	13

Askov straw disposal experiment	Denmark	55.28	9.06	Atlantic	Humid	1.26	8.4	945	11.8
R20 Lanna	Sweden	58.35	13.13	Boreal	Humid	0.79	6	743	43
L10 Ultuna	Sweden	59.80	17.80	Boreal	Humid	0.74	5.4	570	37
LUGAT06V135.1	Italy	45.35	11.97	Continental	Humid	0.74	12.8	850	29.2
R20 Lonnstorp	Sweden	55.66	13.08	Boreal	Humid	0.88	8	717	13
R20 Robacksdalen	Sweden	63.80	20.22	Boreal	Humid	1.00	3	694	8
R20 Saby	Sweden	59.82	17.70	Boreal	Humid	0.77	6	609	35
Experimetal farm near As Straw	Norway	59.65	10.78	Boreal	Humid	1.06	5	881	25
Cologne	Germany	50.93	6.95	Atlantic	Humid	0.89	9	1093	13.7
Trutnov	Czech Republic	50.55	15.88	Continental	Humid	0.73	7.5	750	18.1
Doazit	France	43.92	-0.50	Atlantic	Humid	0.86	13	762	12
Serreslous	France	43.66	-0.65	Atlantic	Humid	0.86	13	979	12.1
KISMA13V59.1	Hungary	46.77	17.23	Pannonian	Dry sub-humid	0.61	10.8	683	27
9_University of Perugia farm Papiano	Italy	42.96	12.38				13.2	831	28.3
Rakican	Slovenia	46.63	14.18	Alpine	Humid	1.25	10.4	798	14.57

Table A6: Information about each pair and variables used in the analysis different for each pair (e.g., SOC of the control, EF, management variables)

Database version:		Crop residues incorporation vs removal								
Experiment ID	treatid_C	treatid_T	Treatment definition_C	Treatment definition_T	Soil depth (cm)	Duration of treatment (years)	SOC_C (Mg ha-1)	EF	crop rotation cereals (%)	Crop incorporated/not removed types
VE-5	L+GM+S(40)	L+GM+S(40)	Limed soil with manure 40 t ha-1	Limed soil with green manure + straw (in 40 t ha-1 manure background)	20	60	53.45	0.99	0.4	winter wheat - lupinus-rapeseed - spring barley - Clover/Trifolium sp.
Rutzendorf_17	incorporated	incorporated	Crop Residues Removed	Crop Residues Incorporated	25	38	65.94	1.03	0.53	Sugar beet - Spring barley - Winter rye - Winter barley - Pea - Winter wheat -

										Sunflower- Soybean - Rapeseed - Spring wheat - Maize - Potato
Rottenhaus_17	incorporated	incorporated	Crop Residues Removed	Crop Residues Incorporated	25	34	31.90	1.09	0.55	Spring barley - Winter wheat - Rapeseed - Field bean - Winter barley - Soybean - Potato - Maize - Pea - Sugar beet - Oat
Jable	Jable All straw of each crop + CC ploughed in, 300 kg N/ha for maize, 195 kg N/ha WW, 165 kg N/ha WB	Jable All straw of each crop + CC ploughed in, 300 kg N/ha for maize, 195 kg N/ha WW, 165 kg N/ha WB	Control without organic fertilization, 300 kg N/ha for maize, 195 kg N/ha for winter wheat, 165 kg N/ha for winter barley	All straw of each crop + catch crop oilseed mustard ploughed in, 300 kg N/ha for maize, 195 kg N/ha for winter wheat, 165 kg N/ha for winter barley	25	15	53.53	1.07	1	Maize - winter wheat - winter barley - catch crop (oilseed mustard)
CENTS_Flakkebjerg	StrawIncorporation_Plowing	StrawIncorporation_Plowing	Removal of straw and mouldboard plowing	Straw incorporation and mouldboard plowing	25	17	51.64	0.97	0.88	Loliums - Oilseed radish - Winter wheat - Spring barley - Pea - Winter barley - Oat - Broad bean
CENTS_Foulum	StrawIncorporation_Plowing	StrawIncorporation_Plowing	Removal of straw and mouldboard plowing	Straw incorporation and mouldboard plowing	25	17	54.91	1.26	1	Ryegrass - Oilseed radish - Winter wheat - Spring barley - Pea - Winter barley - Oat - Broad bean
MATTSO_2a	C	C	Crop rotation of sugar beets - spring barley - clover/grass ley - winter	Crop rotation of sugar beets - spring barley - winter oil seed - winter wheat; all harvest residues chopped	20	53	83.63	0.90	0.5	sugar beets - spring barley - winter oil seed - winter wheat

			wheat; all harvest residues removed. Manure applied	and incorporated where they were produced						
MATTSO_2b	C	C	Crop rotation of sugar beets – spring barley – clover/grass ley – winter wheat; all harvest residues removed. Manure applied	Crop rotation of sugar beets – spring barley – winter oil seed – winter wheat; all harvest residues chopped and incorporated where they were produced	20	53	39.90	0.87	0.5	sugar beets - spring barley - winter oil seed - winter wheat
mulch_Ruprechtshofen	mulch_rotation	mulch_rotation	no mulch and rotation	mulch and rotation	15	5	27.97	0.96	0.5	Vetch - Maize
Revilheira Farm	NT+S	NT+S	No-till with removal of cereal straw	No-till with cereal straw retained	30	11	33.12	1.42	0.75	Lupin - Wheat- Oat- Barley
67_Jokioinen	CT-S	CT-S	conventional tillage and straw removal	conventional tillage and no straw removal	20	30	59.08	1.02	1	Spring wheat - Winter wheat - Oat - Barley - Maize
8_University of Bologna farm Cadriano	t4	t4	maize-wheat rotation with no organic fertilizer	maize-wheat rotation with buring of crop residue	40	34	25.20	1.19	1	Maize- Winter wheat
HAZAR09V29.1	M1	M1	Mouldboard, straw removed	Mouldboard, straw incorporated	25	12	97.68	0.99	1	Wheat
POWLS11V103.2a	S1	S1	No straw incorporation (control plot) in Rothamsted	5 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ straw (winter wheat or winter oilseed rape in 1992) incorporated to 23 cm depth in Rothamsted	23	22	55.61	1.05	1	winter wheat or winter oilseed rape
POWLS11V103.2b	S1	S1	No straw incorporation (control plot) in Woburn	4 t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ straw (winter wheat or winter oilseed rape in 1992) incorporated to 23 cm depth in Woburn	23	22	29.90	1.10	1	winter wheat or winter oilseed rape
Osaker	Osaker Straw ploughed in, N2	Osaker Straw ploughed in, N2			20	21	54.33	1.05	1	barley - oats - springwheat

Longs Tours	RR	RR	residue export	residue retention	27	53	33.39	1.10	0.75	White mustard - Vetch - Sugar beet- Winter wheat - Winter barley
lteFertBS	LTE Braunschweig NPK + Straw	LTE Braunschweig NPK + Straw	Without organic fertilisation, application of N fertilisation in different stages (N1, N2, N3; fertilisation of winter wheat in the year 2000)	With straw (organic fertilisation) to root and tuber crops, application of N fertilisation in different stages (N1, N2, N3; fertilisation of winter wheat in the year 2000)	20	49	41.46	1.21		With straw (organic fertilisation) to root and tuber crops, winter wheat,
MANOJ08V54.2	CC F + HR	CC F + HR	continuous corn, no organic fertilization	continuous corn, harvest residues	30	32	61.77	1.10	1	Maize
Harste	residues left	residues left	residues removed	residues left	20	14	33.31	1.04	0.5	Sinapis alba - Sugar beets - Winter wheat
Teagasc	RI CT	RI CT	residues removed, conventional tillage	residues incorporated, conventional tillage	30	9	60.10	1.08	1	winter wheat
Torrepadierne	MT_R1	MT_R1	CT+1994-2001:cereal-fallow/2001-2004:cereal-legume-cereal-cereal	MT+1994-2001:cereal-fallow/2001-2004:cereal-legume-cereal-cereal	20	10	25.16	1.32	0.75	Winter barley - Vetch - Winter wheat
DOTN-3	CT with moderate N with straw	CT with moderate N with straw	Conventional tillage moderate rates N fertilizers straw removed	Conventional tillage moderate rates N fertilizers straw returned	10	17	16.82	0.92	0.6	Winter wheat - Spring barley - Horse bean- Spring wheat - Triticale
Askov straw disposal experiment	Straw4	Straw4	Removal of straw	Incorporation of 4 Mg straw/ha/year	20	38	41.45	1.14	1	Spring barley
R20 Lanna	Lanna_SI_80	Lanna_SI_80	straw removed, 80 kg N	straw incorporated, 80 kg N	20	27	46.90	1.03	1	Spring barley - Oat/Avena sativa - Winter wheat
L10 Ultuna	Ultuna_SI_80	Ultuna_SI_80	straw burnt, 80 kg N	straw incorporated, 80 kg N	20	53	33.25	1.39	0.75	Spring barley - Maize - Oat - Wheat- Rapeseed
LUGAT06V135.1	RI N120	RI N120	residue removal + 120 N kg/ha	residue incorporation + 120 N kg/ha	30	40	45.80	1.07	0.5	Maize

R20 Lonnstorp	Lönnstorp SI_0	Lönnstorp SI_0	straw removed, 0 kg N	straw incorporated, 80 kg N	20	32	32.90	1.24	1	Spring barley, Oat, Spring wheat, Winter wheat
R20 Robacksdalen	Röbäcksdalen SI_0	Röbäcksdalen SI_0	straw removed, 0 kg N	straw incorporated, 80 kg N	20	28	56.70	1.02	1	Spring barley, Oat
R20 Saby	Säby_SI_1 20	Säby_SI_1 20	straw removed, 0 kg N	straw incorporated, 120 kg N	20	42	54.50	1.06	1	Spring barley - Oat - Spring wheat - Winter wheat
Experminetal farm near As Straw	As Straw ploughed in, N0	As Straw ploughed in, N0	Straw removed, N0	Straw ploughed in, N2	20	23	72.03	1.02	1	winter wheat
Cologne	Cologne mineral + residues	Cologne mineral + residues	mineral only	mineral + residues	20	31	14.74	1.04	0.6	
Trutnov	Trutnov Straw N + NPK	Trutnov Straw N + NPK	Trutnov NPK	Trutnov Straw N + NPK	20	44	35.85	1.02	0.6	
Doazit	Doazit TR	Doazit TR	maize, residues removed	maize for grain, residues returned to soil	25	21	32.19	1.10	1	Maize
Serreslous	Serreslous TR	Serreslous TR	maize, residues removed	maize for grain, residues returned to soil	25	24	24.93	1.14	1	Maize
KISMA13V59.1	NPK+SM	NPK+SM	nitrogen fertilizer	nitrogen + straw	30	23	50.49	1.14	1	maize - winter wheat - winter barley
9_University of Perugia farm Papiano	burial	burial			40	43	41.08	1.14	0.75	Wheat - sugar beet - sunflower - pea - grain sorghum - faba bean - maize
Rakican	Rakican All straw of each crop ploughed in, 165 kg N/ha	Rakican All straw of each crop ploughed in, 165 kg N/ha	Control without organic fertilization, 165 kg N/ha mineral fertilizer	All straw of each crop ploughed in, 165 kg N/ha	25	25	39.19	1.13	1	maize (before catch crop oilseed mustard) - winter wheat - barley

Data to support the analysis of Chapter 7: Tillage

Inversion vs. Non-inversion tillage

Table A7: Experiment information and variables used in the analysis similar for all treatments within the experiment (Climate and soil variables)

Database version: 24.10.2022										
Inversion tillage vs. Non-inversion Tillage										
Experiment ID	Country	Latitude (decimal degrees)	Longitude (decimal degrees)	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Average aridity index	Annual mean temperature (°C)	Annual precipitation (mm)	Clay (%)	Soil type (USDA)
Fuchsenbigl_90	Austria	48.2	16.8	Continental	Dry sub-humid	0.581	10.1	602	22.0	Loam
BOPACT	Belgium	50.99	3.77	Atlantic	Humid	0.946	10.6	794	5.3	Sandy Loam
Rnhave	Denmark	55.0	9.8	Continental	Humid	1.092	8.5	776	17.4	Silt Loam
Hjer	Denmark	55.0	8.7	Atlantic	Humid	1.169	8.5	801	15.6	Sandy Loam
Bramstrup	Denmark	55.3	10.4	Continental	Humid	0.807	8.5	618	12.8	Silt Loam
Jerslev	Denmark	55.6	11.2	Continental	Humid	0.757	8.5	578	16.5	Silt Loam
Jyndevad	Denmark	54.5	9.1	Atlantic	Humid	1.168	8.5	824	4.7	Sand
Nakskov	Denmark	54.8	11.1	Continental	Humid	0.779	8.7	578	18.0	Loam
Jokioinen 3	Finland	60.2	24.2	Boreal	Humid	0.965	4.8	664	58.0	Clay
67_Jokioinen	Finland			Boreal	Humid	0.965	4.8	664	41.2	Clay
Biberach	Germany	48.1	9.8	Continental	Humid	1.075	8.0	894	18.1	Silt Loam
Dossenheim	Germany	49.5	8.6	Continental	Humid	0.790	10.8	738	30.1	Clay Loam
Edelweiler	Germany	48.5	8.5	Continental	Humid	1.634	7.6	1309	19.3	Loam
Efringen-Kirchen	Germany	49.6	7.6	Continental	Humid	0.758	9.3	640	22.1	Silt Loam
Eisighof	Germany	48.1	9.4	Continental	Humid	1.012	7.6	812	28.3	Silty Clay Loam
Grunsfeld	Germany	49.6	9.7	Continental	Humid	0.826	8.9	714	55.7	Silty Clay
Hechingen	Germany	48.4	9.0	Continental	Humid	0.948	8.2	807	63.8	Clay
Ihinger Hof	Germany	48.7	8.9	Continental	Humid	0.914	8.6	797	21.0	Silt Loam
Kirchhausen	Germany	49.2	9.1	Continental	Humid	0.928	9.6	825	20.8	Silt Loam
Oberndorf	Germany	48.3	8.6	Continental	Humid	1.109	7.8	914	42.4	Silty Clay
Odenheim	Germany	49.2	8.8	Continental	Humid	0.956	9.8	849	15.7	Silt Loam
Untergrombach	Germany	49.1	8.2	Continental	Humid	0.844	10.2	747	9.0	Sandy Loam
Weikersheim	Germany	49.5	10.0	Continental	Humid	0.896	8.5	772	34.2	Silty Clay Loam
JOSCH12V58.1	Germany	52.5	14.3	Continental	Dry sub-humid	0.584	9.0	503	7.0	Loamy Sand

Kleinhohenheim	Germany	48.7	9.2	Continental	Humid	0.840	8.9	740	30.0	Sandy Clay Loam
Carlow	Ireland	52.8	-6.9	Atlantic	Humid	1.219	10.1	884	5.0	Sandy Loam
Fagna	Italy	44.0	11.4	Continental	Humid	0.945	13.3	1104	16.0	Loam
BASIS	Netherlands	52.5	5.5	Atlantic	Humid	0.999	9.6	778		
Revilheira Farm	Portugal	38.5	-7.5	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.347	15.8	580	31.1	Clay Loam
SIMAN08V100.1	Slovakia	42.0	12.5	Mediterranean	Dry sub-humid	0.526	15.7	680	15.1	Loam
Rasica	Slovenia	46.1	15.1	Continental	Humid	1.528	10.9	926	16.8	Loam
TillComp	Slovenia	46.1	14.5	Continental	Humid	1.569	9.6	1413	28.0	Silty Clay Loam
MADEJ09V105.2a_Lle	Spain	41.8	1.3	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.441	13.2	613	13.0	Silt Loam
MADEJ09V105.2a_Za	Spain	41.8	-0.8	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.228	15.0	381	22.3	Loam
GOMEZ12V124.1	Spain	43.1	-7.5	Atlantic	Humid	1.300	12.0	1394	14.5	Loam
12_La Higuera	Spain	40.1	-4.4	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.210	15.3	332	26.8	Silty Clay Loam
43_EEAD Experimental Station	Spain	41.5	-0.5	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.219	15.5	359	22.3	Loam
El Encin	Spain	40.5	-3.4	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.285	14.1	434	21.0	Loam
Torrepadierne	Spain	42.2	-4.4	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.333	11.7	430	24.6	Loam
Olite	Spain	42.5	-1.8	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.403	13.3	548	41.3	Silty Clay
INIA-LTE-ROT	Spain	40.5	-3.3	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.282	13.9	428	12.3	Silt Loam
Seville	Spain	37.3	-6.1	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.313	18.1	535	24.0	Silt Loam
MMENA20_wheat	Spain	37.9	-1.7	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.232	13.8	388	30.9	Sandy Clay Loam
Malm	Sweden	55.7	13.1	Continental	Humid	0.760	8.3	585	17.4	Silt Loam
Tanikon	Switzerland	47.5	8.9	Continental	Humid	1.350	8.0	1164	16.0	Sandy Loam
Frick	Switzerland	47.5	8.0	Continental	Humid	1.286	9.6	1136	45.0	Clay
HAZAR09V29.1	United Kingdom	50.8	-4.0	Atlantic	Humid	1.398	9.9	1102	11.0	Silt

Table A8: Information about each pair and variables used in the analysis different for each pair (e.g., SOC of the control, EF, management variables)

Database version: 24.10.2022		Inversion tillage vs. Non-inversion Tillage						
Experiment ID	treatid_C	treatid_T	Treatment definition_C	Treatment definition_T	Soil depth (cm)	Duration of treatment (years)	SOC_C (Mg ha ⁻¹)	EF
Fuchsenbigl_90	Conventional	Reduced Tillage	Conventional tillage	Reduced tillage	30	30	74.0	1.13
Fuchsenbigl_90	Conventional	Minimum Tillage	Conventional tillage	Minimum tillage	30	30	74.0	1.14
BOPACT	Comp + CT + cattle slurry	Comp + NT + cattle slurry	Yearly application of farm compost + conventional tillage + yearly application of cattle slurry	Yearly application of farm compost + non-inversion tillage + yearly application of cattle slurry	30	7	45.7	1.07
Rnhave	B	C	Ploughing to 20 cm, Seedbed preparation by harrowing 3-5 cm, Undersown cover crop	Seedbed preparation by rotovating 3-5 cm, Undersown cover crop	20	10	4.5	0.97
Hjer	A	F	Stubble cultivation 10-12 cm, Ploughing to 20 cm, Seedbed preparation by harrowing 3-5 cm	Stubble cultivation 10-12 cm, Seedbed preparation by harrowing 3-5 cm	20	18	5.2	1.07
Hjer	B	C	Ploughing to 20 cm, Seedbed preparation by harrowing 3-5 cm, Undersown cover crop	Seedbed preparation by rotovating 3-5 cm, Undersown cover crop	20	18	5.7	1.10
Bramstrup	MP	ST	Mouldboard ploughing; typically, 25 cm	Shallow tillage; Stubble tillage followed by a hoe tine seeder	22	8	34.3	1.23
Jerslev	MP	ST	Mouldboard ploughing; typically, 25 cm	Shallow tillage; Disc harrow followed by traditional drill	22	5	96.6	0.96
Malm	MP	ST	Mouldboard ploughing; typically, 25 cm	Shallow tillage; Stubble tillage followed by Wäderstad Rapid disc drill	22	30	51.9	1.14
Nakskov	MP	ST	Mouldboard ploughing; typically, 25 cm	Shallow tillage; Stubble tillage followed by Wäderstad Rapid disc drill	22	5	42.8	1.09
Jokioinen 3	CT	RT	Ploughing with grass in cereal rotation	ridge tillage with cereal rotation	20	29	59.1	0.94
67_Jokioinen	CT-SB	RT-SB	conventional tillage and straw burning	reduced tillage and straw burning	20	30	58.8	0.97

67_Jokioinen	CT-SR	RT-SR	conventional tillage and straw removal	reduced tillage and straw removal	20	30	58.8	0.95
67_Jokioinen	CT-S	RT-S	conventional tillage and no straw removal	reduced tillage and no straw removal	20	30	57.8	0.98
Biberach	Bib_PT	Bib_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	10	35.3	1.08
Dossenheim	Dos_PT	Dos_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	10	23.4	0.91
Edelweiler	Ede_PT	Ede_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	15	49.0	1.14
Efringen-Kirchen	Efr_PT	Efr_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	10	52.4	1.09
Eisighof	Eis_PT	Eis_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	5	52.8	1.09
Grunsfeld	Grn_PT	Grn_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	10	38.2	1.29
Hechingen	Hech_PT	Hech_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	18	81.2	1.01
Ihinger Hof	Ihi_PT	Ihi_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	6	23.3	1.10
Kirchhausen	Kir_PT	Kir_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	10	23.7	1.16
Oberndorf	Ober_PT	Ober_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	10	48.4	1.14
Odenheim	Oden_PT	Oden_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	10	14.5	1.18
Untergrombach	Unt_PT	Unt_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	17	29.0	0.93
Weikersheim	Weik_PT	Weik_RT	plow tillage	reduced tillage	20	15	43.4	0.84
JOSCH12V58.1	CT	RT			30	9	31.3	1.12
Kleinhohenheim	Kleinhohe nheim DP	Kleinhohen heim chisel plow	deep mouldboard plow, complete inversion 25 cm	loosens top 15 cm without inversion	20	12	34.8	1.24
Kleinhohenheim	Kleinhohe nheim DLP	Kleinhohen heim chisel plow	double layer plow, inverts top 15cm and loosens 15-25 cm by chisel goose foot	loosens top 15 cm without inversion	20	12	36.1	1.19
Kleinhohenheim	Kleinhohe nheim SP	Kleinhohen heim chisel plow	shallow mouldboard plow, inverts top 15 cm	loosens top 15 cm without inversion	20	12	41.9	1.03
Carlow	Carlow CT	Carlow RT	conventional tillage (25-30 cm depth)	reduced tillage (7-10 cm depth)	20	8	59.3	1.05
Fagna	Fagna CT	Fagna MT	conventional tillage (40 cm depth)	minimum tillage (10-15 cm depth)	40	8	57.8	1.06
BASIS	Organic Standard	Organic Minimal	No pesticides; standard refers to ploughing method (see tillage tab)	No pesticides; minimal refers to ploughing method (see tillage tab)	30	7		1.06
BASIS	Common Standard	Common Minimal	use of pesticides; standard refers to ploughing method (see tillage tab)	use of pesticides; minimal refers to ploughing method (see tillage tab)	30	7		1.06

Revilheira Farm	CT	RT	Conventional tillage based on moldboard plough (25 cm) + disc harrow with removal of cereal straw	Reduced tillage based on non-inversion tine cultivation with removal of cereal straw	30	11	31.3	1.05
SIMAN08V100.1	CT	RT	conventional tillage to 22-25 cm depth	reduced tillage, disking to a depth of 10-12 cm	30	13	51.9	1.02
Rasica	CT	MT	Inversion tillage, Moldboard plowing	Non-inversion tillage, Harrowing	20	21	39.3	1.17
TillComp	NPK-T	NPK-NT	fertilization by NPK fertilizers (all treatments receive approx. the same amount of N)	fertilization by NPK fertilizers (all treatments receive approx. the same amount of N)	30	13	53.1	1.13
TillComp	K+1/2NPK-T	K+1/2NPK-NT	compost plus half N compared to NPK	compost plus half N compared to NPK	30	13	58.9	1.27
TillComp	K-T	K-NT	just compost (approx. equal application of N as with NPK)	just compost (approx. equal application of N as with NPK)	30	13	53.4	1.53
TillComp	Control-T	Control-NT	no fertilization	no fertilization	30	13	51.5	1.24
MADEJ09V105.2a_Lle	TT_Lle	RT_Lle	Traditional tillage	Reduced tillage	25	10	33.7	1.19
MADEJ09V105.2a_Za	TT_Za	RT_Za	Traditional tillage	Reduced tillage	25	16	21.8	1.05
GOMEZ12V124.1	PT	CT	Conventional plow tillage	Conservation tillage	15	14	68.1	1.21
12_La Higuera	CT	MT	conventional tillage with moldboard plow	minimum tillage with chisel plow	30	16	26.5	0.98
43_EEAD Experimental Station	CC_CT	CC_RT	Monoculture + conventional tillage	Monoculture + reduced tillage	30	16	41.0	1.05
El Encin	CT	MT	Conventional tillage	Minimum tillage	30	20	31.7	1.02
Torrepadierne	CT	MT	conventional tillage	minimum tillage	30	10	40.0	1.22
Olite	CT	MT	Conventional tillage	Minimum tillage	15	18	21.2	1.35
INIA-LTE-ROT	CT-Monocrop	MT-Monocrop	wheat monocrop in Conventional tillage	wheat monocrop in Minimum tillage	30	19	30.8	0.77
INIA-LTE-ROT	CT-Rot	MT-Rot	4-year rotation in Conventional tillage	4-year rotation in Minimum tillage	30	19	26.7	0.94
Seville	TT	RT	Traditional tillage	Reduced/conservation tillage	25	20	35.4	1.20
MMENA20_wheat	CT_wheat	RT_wheat	Conventional tillage	Reduced tillage	20	14	18.4	1.40
Jyndevid	MP	ST	Mouldboard ploughing; typically ,25 cm	Shallow tillage; Direct drilling with a combined tine harrow/drill	22	36	67.8	1.06
Tanikon	PL	CH	Mouldboard plough	Chisel	20	13	49.7	1.00

Frick	CT MC without	RT MC without	no preparation + composted manure/slurry + plough	no preparation + composted manure/slurry + reduced tillage	20	16	53.9	1.14
Frick	CT MC with	RT MC with	with preparation + composted manure/slurry + plough	with preparation + composted manure/slurry + reduced tillage	20	16	54.3	1.11
Frick	CT SL without	RT SL without	no preparation + slurry + plough	no preparation + slurry + reduced tillage	20	16	52.9	1.11
Frick	CT SL with	RT SL with	with preparation + slurry + plough	with preparation + slurry + reduced tillage	20	16	53.4	1.69
HAZAR09V29.1	M1	CT1	Mouldboard, straw incorporated	Chisel plough, straw incorporated	25	12	90.3	0.82
HAZAR09V29.1	M2	CT2	Mouldboard, straw removed	Chisel plough, straw removed	25	12	86.4	0.86

Inversion vs. Zero-Tillage

Table A9: Experiment information and variables used in the analysis similar for all treatments within the experiment (Climate and soil variables)

Database version: 24.10.2022										
Inversion vs. Zero-Tillage										
Experiment ID	Country	Latitude (decimal degrees)	Longitude (decimal degrees)	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Average aridity index	Annual mean temperature (°C)	Annual precipitation (mm)	Clay (%)	Soil type (USDA)
SIMON09V105.1	Czech Republic	50.10	14.26	Continental	Dry sub-humid	0.584	8.1	499	23.4	Silt Loam
CENTS_Flakkebjerg	Denmark	55.32	11.38	Continental	Humid	0.771	8.6	599	15.0	Sandy Loam
DIMAS13V169.1	France	48.33	2.38	Atlantic	Humid	0.659	10.7	631	23.8	Sandy Clay Loam
TEBRU99V53.1	Germany	50.65	9.16	Continental	Humid	1.056	8.2	848	31.0	Sandy Clay Loam
JETF	Hungary	47.43	19.36	Pannonian	Semi-Arid	0.483	10.2	527	34.0	Silty Clay Loam
15_University of Pisa experimental farm	Italy	43.67	10.32	Mediterranean	Humid	0.655	14.2	838	15.5	Loam
Pietranera	Italy	37.50	13.52	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.291	17.3	456	47.1	Clay
CMLL	Lithuania	55.23	23.52	Boreal	Humid	0.856	6.3	616	20.4	Loam
Experimetal farm near As Tillage	Norway	59.65	10.78	Boreal	Humid	1.056	5.8	788	20.0	Loam
Revilheira Farm	Portugal	38.47	-7.47	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.347	15.8	580	20.0	Loam
12_La Higuera	Spain	40.06	-4.43	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.210	15.3	332	26.8	silty Clay Loam
43_EEAD Experimental Station	Spain	41.45	-0.45	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.219	15.5	359	22.3	Loam
BLANC12V189.2aArt	Spain	42.60	-0.99	Mediterranean	Dry sub-humid	0.527	12.9	695	24.2	Loam
BLANC12V189.2aTdA	Spain	41.96	-0.08	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.306	14.6	496	13.5	Sandy Loam
BLANC12V189.2aUdL	Spain	42.56	-1.12	Mediterranean	Dry sub-humid	0.563	11.2	721	35.4	Silty Clay Loam

FERNANDEZUGALDE2009	Spain	42.39	-1.54	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.382	13.7	543	26.0	Silt Loam
INIA-LTE-ROT	Spain	40.53	-3.33	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.282	13.9	428	14.9	Loam
LTE TOMEJIL	Spain	37.40	-5.58	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.312	17.9	560	30.5	Loam
MADEJ09V105.2a_Lle	Spain	41.83	1.28	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.441	13.2	613	13.0	Silt Loam
Malagon	Spain	37.76	-4.54	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.303	17.7	534	69.4	Clay
Olite	Spain	42.46	-1.82	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.403	13.3	548	39.5	Clay Loam
Zamaduenas	Spain	41.75	-4.75	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.319	12.2	437	19.4	Silt Loam
ZUAZO20	Spain	36.92	-3.49	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.249	15.4	417	20.0	Sandy Clay Loam
Oberacker	Switzerland	46.99	7.46	Continental	Humid	1.129	9.0	1042	18.0	Sandy Loam
Tanikon	Switzerland	47.47	8.90	Continental	Humid	1.350	8.0	1164	16.0	Sandy Loam
Boxworth_ADnotill	United Kingdom	52.25	-0.03	Atlantic	Humid	0.710	9.7	576	43.0	Clay
HAZAR09V29.1	United Kingdom	50.77	-3.99	Atlantic	Humid	1.398	9.9	1102	11.0	Silt
Leeds_ADnotill	United Kingdom	53.80	-1.56	Atlantic	Humid	0.941	9.5	702	26.0	Loam
Rothemstedt_ADnotill	United Kingdom	51.80	-0.30	Atlantic	Humid	0.840	9.7	664	20.0	Silt Loam

Table A10: Information about each pair and variables used in the analysis different for each pair (e.g., SOC of the control, EF, management variables)

Database version: 24.10.2022		Inversion vs. Zero-Tillage						
Experiment ID	treatid_C	treatid_T	Treatment definition_C	Treatment definition_T	Soil depth (cm)	Duration of treatment (years)	SOC_C (Mg ha ⁻¹)	EF
SIMON09V105.1	CT	NT	conventional tillage	no till	30	12	62.8	1.10
SIMON09V105.1	CT	NTM	conventional tillage	no till+mulch	30	12	62.8	1.08
CENTS_Flakkebjerg	StrawRem_Plowing	StrawRem_No-till	Removal of straw and mouldboard plowing	Removal of straw and no-till	25	17	49.1	1.10
CENTS_Flakkebjerg	StrawIncor_Plowing	StrawIncor_No-till	Straw incorporation and mouldboard plowing	Straw incorporation and no-till	25	7	48.8	1.10
DIMAS13V169.1	CFIT	CNT	Continuous full inversion tillage	Continuous no till	29	20	67.9	1.10
DIMAS13V169.1	NFIT	CNT	New FIT following NT	Continuous no till	29	20	63.8	1.17
TEBRU99V53.1	CT	NT	conventional tillage 25cm	no tillage, 3cm for seed bed preparation	25	11	23.9	1.08
JETF	MP	NT	mouldboard plowing	no-till	30	13	68.4	1.15
Pietranera	WW-CT	WW-NT	ploughing + Continuous durum wheat rotation	no tillage + Continuous durum wheat rotation	15	18	39.4	1.09
15_University of Pisa experimental farm	CT	NT	Inversion tillage	Zero tillage	30	15	46.7	1.39
CMLL	CT+SRem	NT+SRem	Conventional tillage without fertilizers, straw removed	No-tillage without fertilizers, straw removed	30	17	70.5	1.04
Experimetal farm near As Tillage	Conv till cereal	No-till cereal	Conventional tillage (plough in autumn) with 8yr spring barley+4yrs sowing oats+2yrs spring wheat	Direct sowing with 8yr spring barley+4yrs sowing oats+2yrs spring wheat	30	26	77.8	1.14
Revilheira Farm	CT	NT	Conventional tillage based on mouldboard plough (25 cm) + disc harrow with removal of cereal straw	No-till with removal of cereal straw	30	11	31.7	1.18

MADEJ09V105.2a_Lle	TT_Lle	NT_Lle	Traditional tillage	No tillage	25	10	37.0	1.30
BLANC12V189.2aTdA	CT	NT	Conventional tillage	No tillage	20	8	15.6	1.24
BLANC12V189.2aUdL	CT	NT	Conventional tillage	No tillage	20	12	40.9	1.02
BLANC12V189.2aArt	CT	NT	Conventional tillage	No tillage	20	18	32.6	0.97
12_La Higuera	CT	NT	conventional tillage with moldboard plow	no-tillage	30	18	24.6	1.23
43_EEAD Experimental Station	CF_CT	CF_NT	Cereal-fallow + conventional tillage	Cereal-fallow + no tillage	30	16	36.4	1.06
43_EEAD Experimental Station	CC_CT	CC_NT	Monoculture + conventional tillage	Monoculture + no tillage	30	16	40.2	1.15
LTE TOMEJIL	CT	NT	Conventional tillage with 1 mouldboard plough pass/year + cultivator passes to reduce clod size	Direct drilling or seeding without tillage, crop residue left on field	20	26	21.8	1.18
LTE TOMEJIL	CT	NT	Conventional tillage with 1 mouldboard plough pass/year + cultivator passes to reduce clod size	Direct drilling or seeding without tillage, crop residue left on field	20	26	22.2	1.33
Olite	CT	NT	Conventional tillage	No-tillage	15	18	21.5	0.59
Zamaduenas	CT	NT	Conventional Tillage	No tillage	30	6	132.1	1.73
ZUAZO20	CT	ORG_SVC	Conventional tillage without plant covers	Organic system. No-tillage and spontaneous vegetation for entire soil surface	20	68	22.2	1.94
ZUAZO20	CT	ORG_LEC	Conventional tillage without plant covers	Organic system. No-tillage and legume cover crop for entire soil surface	20	68	22.2	1.67
ZUAZO20	CT	INT_NSS	Conventional tillage without plant covers	Integrated system. No-tillage with spontaneous vegetation strips	20	68	22.2	1.76
ZUAZO20	CT	INT_NLS	Conventional tillage without plant covers	Integrated system. No-tillage with legume strips	20	68	22.2	1.13
FERNANDEZUGALDE2009	CT	NT	Conventional tillage	No-tillage	30	7	39.5	1.00

INIA-LTE-ROT	CT-Monocrop	NT-Monocrop	wheat monocrop in Conventional tillage	wheat monocrop in No tillage	30	19	31.0	1.19
INIA-LTE-ROT	CT-Rot	NT-Rot	4-year rotation in Conventional tillage	4-year rotation in No tillage	30	18	27.5	1.18
Malagon	CT	NT	Conventional tillage	No-tillage	30	27	23.0	1.04
Malagon	CT_wh+su	NT_wh+su	Conventional tillage	No-tillage	30	20	18.2	1.53
vineyard Finca La Grajera	CT	RV	soil with conventional tillage between rows (CT)	a permanent cover crop of resident vegetation (RV), which was dominated by annual grass and forbs common to La Rioja vineyards, including Bromus mollis L., Hordeum murinum L., Diplotaxis eruroides (L.) DC., Sonchus asper (L.) Hill, Sonchus oleraceus L., Veronica latifolia L., Conyza canadensis (L.) Cronquist., and Papaver hybridum L.	25	8	22.4	1.43
Tanikon	PL	NT	Mouldboard plough	NT (no tillage)	20	13	49.7	1.00
Oberacker	MP-GRUD	NT-GRUD	mouldboard ploughing, fertilization concept "GRUD"	no-till, fertilization concept "GRUD"	30	20	56.3	0.94
HAZAR09V29.1	M1	NT1	Mouldboard, straw incorporated	NT, straw incorporated	25	12	92.4	0.95
HAZAR09V29.1	M2	NT2	Mouldboard, straw removed	NT, straw removed	25	12	92.4	0.88
Rothemstedt_A Dnotill	CT	NT	Conventional Tillage	Direct drilled	25	5	47.1	0.99
Boxworth_ADnotill	CT	NT	Conventional Tillage	Direct drilled	25	6	51.2	1.06
Leeds_ADnotill	CT	NT	Conventional Tillage	Direct drilled	25	8	56.5	1.04

Data to support the analysis of Chapter 8: Irrigation

Table A11: Experiment information and variables used in the analysis similar for all treatments within the experiment (Climate and soil variables)

Database version: 03.10.2022										
Irrigation (Non Irrigated vs Irrigated)										
Experiment ID	Country	Latitude (decimal degrees)	Longitude (decimal degrees)	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Average aridity index	Annual mean temperature (°C)	Annual precipitation (mm)	Clay (%)	Soil type (USDA)
ThyrowD1	Germany	52.25	13.23	Continental	Dry sub-humid	0.620	9.1	549	2.7	Loamy sand
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	Italy	41.53	15.55	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.334	15.7	475	26.0	Sandy clay loam
Marchfeld	Austria	48.23	16.80	Continental	Dry sub-humid		9.1	540		Loamy sand

Table A12: Information about each pair and variables used in the analysis different for each pair (e.g., SOC of the control, EF, management variables)

Database version: 03.10.2022								
Irrigation (Non Irrigated vs Irrigated)								
Experiment ID	treatid_C	treatid_T	Treatment definition_C	Treatment definition_T	Soil depth (cm)	Duration of treatment (years)	SOC_C (Mg ha ⁻¹)	EF
ThyrowD1	N1	N1 + irrigation	Zero N	Zero N + irrigation	20.0	39	17.4	1.03
ThyrowD1	N2	N2 + irrigation	Normal N	Normal N + irrigation	20.0	39	20.6	1.03
ThyrowD1	N3	N3 + irrigation	Excessive N	Excessive N + irrigation	20.0	39	21.3	1.02
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t14	t1	CDW - no irrigated	CDW - irrigated	35.0	18	56.9	0.91
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t15	t2	1-yr DWLM - no irrigated	1-yr DWLM - irrigated	35.0	18	76.9	0.87
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t16	t3	2-yr DWLM - no irrigated	2-yr DWLM - irrigated	35.0	18	72.5	0.85
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t17	t4	3-yr DWLM - no irrigated	3-yr DWLM - irrigated	35.0	18	67.9	0.89

6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t18	t5	1-yr DWBM - no irrigated	1-yr DWBM - irrigated	35.0	18	72.9	0.87
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t19	t6	2-yr DWBM - no irrigated	2-yr DWBM - irrigated	35.0	18	67.4	0.91
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t20	t7	3-yr DWBM - no irrigated	3-yr DWBM - irrigated	35.0	18	58.0	1.08
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t21	t8	1-yr LM - no irrigated	1-yr LM - irrigated	35.0	18	72.0	0.91
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t22	t9	2-yr LM - no irrigated	2-yr LM - irrigated	35.0	18	78.9	0.82
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t23	t10	3-yr LM - no irrigated	3-yr LM - irrigated	35.0	18	76.3	0.89
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t24	t11	1-yr BM - no irrigated	1-yr BM - irrigated	35.0	18	67.9	0.85
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t25	t12	2-yr BM - no irrigated	2-yr BM - irrigated	35.0	18	69.4	0.93
6_CREA experimental farm Menichella	t26	t13	3-yr BM - no irrigated	3-yr BM - irrigated	35.0	18	69.1	0.97
Marchfeld	No N	No N+irr	No N	No N+irr	25	27	49,3	0,94
Marchfeld	Medium N	Medium N+irr	Medium N	Medium N+irr	25	27	50,3	0,95
Marchfeld	Optimal N	Optimal N+irr	Optimal N	Optimal N+irr	25	27	53,1	0,94
Marchfeld	Excessive N	Excessive N+irr	Excessive N	Excessive N+irr	25	27	50,4	0,98

Data to support the analysis of Chapter 9: Agroforestry

Table A13: Experiment information and variables used in the analysis similar for all treatments within the experiment (Climate and soil variables)

Database version: 13.03.2023										
Agroforestry with hedges and alley cropping with single trees vs cropland without trees										
Experiment ID	Country	Latitude (decimal degrees)	Longitude (decimal degrees)	Climatic zone	Aridity class	Average aridity index	Annual mean temperature (°C)	Annual precipitation (mm)	Clay (%)	Soil type (USDA)
AF_BE_03	Belgium	50.92	4.90	Atlantic	Humid	0.89	10.3	778	14.94	
Bedfordshire_AF	United Kingdom	52.07	-0.63	Atlantic	Humid	0.86	9.5	646	55.00	
Luzern	Switzerland	47.18	8.12	Continental	Humid	1.42	9.2	1270	18.00	
ID#AAAAMXwqxTU	France	43.72	4.02	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.47	14.3	698	17.60	
ID#AAAAMXwqxTU	France	43.72	4.02	Mediterranean	Semi-Arid	0.47	14.3	698	31.40	
ID#AAAAMXwqxTU_1	France	48.14	3.61	Continental	Humid	0.76	10.0	697	23.96	
AF_BE_02_StPietersLeeuw1	Belgium	50.80	4.21	Atlantic	Humid	0.95	10.2	793	11.39	
AF_BE_02_StPietersLeeuw2	Belgium	50.79	4.21	Atlantic	Humid	0.95	10.2	793	11.39	
AF_BE_02_Haut-Ittre1	Belgium	50.64	4.30	Atlantic	Humid	0.99	9.9	817	18.76	
AF_BE_02_Maarkedal	Belgium	50.82	3.67	Atlantic	Humid	0.97	10.3	791	19.63	
AF_BE_02_Tongeren	Belgium	50.75	5.44	Atlantic	Humid	0.96	9.9	816	18.28	
AF_BE_02_Landen	Belgium	50.73	5.09	Atlantic	Humid	0.89	10.2	771	15.16	
AF_BE_02_Ieper1	Belgium	50.88	2.80	Atlantic	Humid	0.90	10.1	720	13.17	
AF_BE_02_Geraardsbergen	Belgium	50.88	2.79	Atlantic	Humid	0.90	10.1	720	12.21	
AF_BE_02_Herzele	Belgium	50.87	3.91	Atlantic	Humid	0.99	10.1	804	12.98	
AF_BE_02_STeenhuize	Belgium	50.83	3.92	Atlantic	Humid	0.97	10.2	793	13.47	
AF_BE_02_Ieper2	Belgium	50.88	2.79	Atlantic	Humid	0.90	10.1	720	12.21	

Table A14: Information about each pair and variables used in the analysis different for each pair (e.g., SOC of the control, EF, management variables)

Database version: 13.03.2023										
Agroforestry with hedges and alley cropping with single trees vs cropland without trees										
Experiment ID	treatid_C	Climatic zone	Treatment definition_C	Treatment definition_T	Soil depth (cm)	Duration of treatment (years)	SOC_C (Mg ha ⁻¹)	EF	System	Tree species
AF_BE_03	WALT+30m	WALT+3m	cropland	alley_cropping	23		41.39	1.21	alley_cropping	walnut
Bedfordshire_AF	control	all treatments	cropland	alley_cropping	40	19	113.00	1.20	alley_cropping	poplar
Luzern	Acker mitte	AF	cropland	alley_cropping	40	7	165.12	1.23	alley_cropping	apple
ID#AAAAMXwqxTU	C	AIR	cropland	alley_cropping	30	18	41.77	1.02	alley_cropping	walnut
ID#AAAAMXwqxTU	C	ATR	cropland	alley_cropping	30	18	41.77	1.30	alley_cropping	walnut
ID#AAAAMXwqxTU_1	MO18m	MO1m	cropland	hedge_cropland	30		99.57	1.46	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_StPietersLeeuw1	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		46.83	1.15	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_StPietersLeeuw2	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		59.45	0.91	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_Haut-Ittre1	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		35.55	1.27	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_Markedal	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		46.47	1.29	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_Tongeren	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		52.25	1.02	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_Landen	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		63.39	1.32	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_Leper1	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		33.37	1.19	hedge	hedge

AF_BE_02_Geraardsbergen	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		39.94	1.29	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_Herzele	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		35.55	1.81	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_STeenhuize	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		44.66	1.61	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_02_leper2	POPT_plus_30m	POPT_plus_3m	cropland	hedge_cropland	23		60.53	1.22	hedge	hedge
AF_BE_03	WALT+30m	WALT+3m	cropland	alley_cropping	23		41.39	1.21	alley_cropping	walnut

